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Erica Delugas (CSIL) carried out the overarching analysis, data collection, and draft of the report. Gelsomina Catalano (CSIL) provided overall methodological guidance, contributed to the structuring, content, and revision of the draft, and ensured alignment with the overall CBA methodological framework. Silvia Vignetti (CSIL) provided methodological guidance and comments on the drafting to improve quality. Alessandra Caputo (CSIL) performed the citation and patent analysis and drafted Section 4 of the report. Dimitris Pappas (Opix) contributed to citation and patent analysis by extracting publications and data on patents. Erika Balsyte and Despoina Sousoni (ELIXIR) contributed to data collection, interview schedules and coordination with the UniProt team. Izabella Martins Grapengiesser (Technopolis Group) contributed to the design of the Impact Pathway of UniProt, Section 2 of the report.

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Abbreviations

ADS	Archaeology Data Service
API	Application Programming Interface
BADC	British Atmospheric Data Centre
CBA	Cost Benefit Analysis
EC	European Commission
EBI	European Bioinformatics Institute
ELIXIR	A distributed infrastructure for life-science data
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
ESDS	Economic and Social Data Service
EUR	Euros
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GO	Gene Ontology
IP	Internet Protocol
IP2L	Internet Protocol to Location
NCBI	National Centre for Biotechnology Information
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
OS	Open Science
PathOS	Open Science Impact Pathways
PIR	Protein Information Resource
PSD	Protein Sequence Database
SDGs	United Nations Sustainable Development Goals
SIB	Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
TrEMBL	Translated EMBL Nucleotide Sequence Data Library
UniProt	Universal Protein Resource
UPI	Unique Protein Identifier
USD	United States Dollar
WTP	Willingness to pay

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the assessment of UniProt (*the Universal Protein Resource*), a freely accessible and expertly curated database providing comprehensive protein sequence and functional information. The evaluation combined a tailored Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) to measure short-term, quantifiable impacts with an impact pathway approach to capture UniProt's broader scientific and societal contributions over time.

Focusing on the period from 2017 to 2023, the CBA considered both operational costs incurred by the provider and the costs borne by the user community to update and maintain the resource. The benefits identified were primarily related to efficiency gains for users, measured in terms of time saved and reduced effort compared to a scenario without UniProt. These benefits include savings in transaction costs, such as the time and effort required to negotiate access to alternative data sources; savings in access costs, due to faster retrieval of information made possible by having integrated data available on a single platform rather than across scattered resources; and savings in labour costs, resulting from more efficient analyses and the avoidance of redundant work, thanks to the improved data quality provided by UniProt's manual curation and annotation. The analysis estimated that each user gains between EUR 3,500 and EUR 5,500 annually, demonstrating substantial net benefits.

Beyond these immediate efficiency gains, UniProt supports long-term scientific innovation and knowledge creation. From 2003 to 2022, over 15,000 scientific publications referenced UniProt, particularly in medical and health sciences, contributing to sustainable development goals such as good health and zero hunger. The resource's influence extends to industry as well, with more than 183,000 patent documents between 1988 and 2022 citing UniProt-related data, mainly in biotechnology and pharmaceuticals. Qualitative evidence further highlights UniProt's role in fostering collaborations between academia and industry, supporting start-ups and spin-offs that depend heavily on its data.

This assessment underscores the challenges of evaluating open science infrastructures. It is difficult to precisely estimate user numbers and define counterfactual scenarios, and attributing costs and benefits in a collaborative ecosystem adds complexity. Despite these hurdles, the analysis clearly shows that UniProt delivers significant net value through time savings and improved data quality, while also contributing to long-term research advancements and societal benefits. These findings reinforce the importance of ongoing support for open, community-driven scientific resources like UniProt.

Introduction

This case study focuses on the impact assessment of **UniProt**, a freely accessible knowledge base that provides protein sequence and functional data to the scientific community and industrial users. The assessment applies a cost-benefit analysis approach in combination with an impact pathways approach.¹ The study employs a range of data collection and analytical methods, as shown in Figure 1 and detailed in Annex 1. Quantitative evidence was primarily used to carry out the cost-benefit analysis, while qualitative evidence helped to uncover the mechanisms underlying the causal pathways associated with UniProt and to provide a more nuanced interpretation of the outcomes identified in the impact pathway logic.

Figure 1 Assessing the value of UniProt: the methodological toolkit

Source: Authors

The findings of this assessment are structured as follows: Section 1 introduces UniProt and its use. Section 2 details the impact pathways that have been identified in the exploitation of UniProt. Section 3 presents the findings from the cost-benefit analysis. Section 4 explores

¹ A pathway represents the chain of events according to which RI's research-related activities might generate effects on its stakeholders' ecosystem. It entails resources, activity, outputs, outcomes and later impacts. See section 2 for more details.

additional impacts evaluated through other methodologies (e.g. citation and patent analysis, interviews and focus groups). Lastly, Section 5 offers conclusions and highlights the main challenges encountered and lessons learnt during the assessment.

1. UniProt: a catalogue of proteins

1.1. The database

UniProt - the Universal Protein Resource - is a **freely accessible knowledge base resource** that provides protein sequence and functional information, with many entries sourced from genome sequencing projects. It includes extensive details on the biological functions of proteins derived from research literature. It is organised into **four core databases**, including UniProtKB (with sub-parts Swiss-Prot and TrEMBL), UniParc, UniRef and Proteome (see Box 1 for more details).

UniProt data are updated roughly every eight weeks, leading to around six releases annually, with its expansion showing no signs of slowing down. UniProtKB – one of the most widely known and utilised datasets, contains over 250 million entries², showing significant growth from the 80 million entries recorded in 2014³. This extensive dataset now requires around 1 petabyte of storage space.

Box 1 UniProt structure

² As of the latest release, 2025_01

³ UniProt Consortium (2015)

specific protein within its entry or browse a comprehensive database of cross-references. As of the latest release 2025_01, UniProtKB includes 253,206,171 entries for sequences. It consists of two datasets:

UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot: it is a manually annotated, non-redundant protein sequence database. It combines information extracted from scientific literature and biocurator-evaluated computational analysis. It provides all known relevant information about a particular protein (e.g. functions, structures, post-translational modifications, interactions, etc.). Annotation is regularly reviewed to keep up with current scientific findings. The manual annotation of an entry involves a detailed analysis of the protein sequence and of the scientific literature. Annotated entries undergo quality assurance before inclusion into UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot. As of the latest release, 2025_01, UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot contains 572,970 sequence entries.

UniProtKB/TrEMBL: it consists of automatically annotated entries that have not undergone manual review. It was introduced in response to increased dataflow resulting from genome projects, as the time- and labour-consuming manual annotation process of UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot could not be broadened to include all available protein sequences. It contains sequences from Protein Data Bank, gene prediction (e.g. Ensembl, RefSeq and ENA), and structures predicted with AlphaFold2. As of the latest release, 2025_01, UniProtKB/TrEMBL contains 252,633,201 sequence entries.

(2) **UniParc (UniProt Archive)** is a comprehensive and non-redundant archive of all protein sequences from the main publicly available protein sequence databases⁴, including those outside UniProtKB. Proteins may exist in several different source databases and in multiple copies in the same database. In order to avoid redundancy, UniParc stores each unique sequence only once. Identical sequences are merged, regardless of whether they are from the same or different species. Each sequence is given a stable and unique identifier (UPI), making it possible to identify the same protein from different source databases. UniParc contains only protein sequences with no annotation. Database cross-references in UniParc entries allow further information about the protein to be retrieved from the source databases. When sequences in the source databases change, these changes are tracked by UniParc and the history of all changes is archived. As of the latest release, 2025_01, 833,496,420 sequences are provided by UniParc.

(3) **UniRef (UniProt Reference Clusters)** provides clustered sets of sequences from UniProtKB and selected UniParc records. This helps compress sequence redundancy and speed up sequence similarity searches. Specifically, it provides three resolutions for faster similarity searches: UniRef100, UniRef90 and UniRef50⁵. As of the latest release, 2025_01, 728,048,531 clusters are available in UniRef.

⁴ A complete list of the source databases is available here <https://www.uniprot.org/uniparc> and <https://www.uniprot.org/help/uniparc>

⁵ UniRef100 combines identical sequences and sub-fragments with 11 or more residues from any organism into a single UniRef entry. UniRef90 is built by clustering UniRef100 sequences such that each cluster is composed of sequences that have at least 90% sequence identity to, and 80% overlap with, the longest sequence in the cluster

(4) **Proteome**⁶: a proteome is a set of proteins thought to be expressed by an organism. UniProt Proteome portal provides protein sequence sets obtained from the translation of completely sequenced genomes. UniProt proteomes may include both manually reviewed (UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot) and unreviewed (UniProtKB/TrEMBL) entries. As of the latest release, 2025_01, 843,388 entries are available on the UniProt Proteome portal.

Source: Authors based on <https://www.uniprot.org/>

This knowledge base is maintained by the UniProt consortium, established in 2001 and includes the [European Bioinformatics Institute](#) (EMBL-EBI), the [Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics](#) (SIB), and the [Protein Information Resource](#) (PIR)⁷. The financial sustainability of UniProt is ensured through the combined efforts of its consortium members and financial backing from several national research institutes⁸. In 2024, funders invested approximately 14.4 million USD to finance UniProt's operations, with the majority of the funds allocated to cover personnel costs.⁹

The database as we know it today (see Box 1 above) was established by the UniProt consortium in 2002 to fulfil the need for a centralised repository of protein information, which was increasingly in demand within the scientific community. However, it is built upon earlier databases that date back to 1984. The Figure below highlights UniProt's most important milestones achieved between 1984 and 2024.

(the seed sequence). UniRef50 is built by clustering UniRef90 seed sequences that have at least 50% sequence identity to, and 80% overlap with, the longest sequence in the cluster. Source: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/online/courses/uniprot-quick-tour/the-uniprot-databases/uniref/>

⁶ <https://www.uniprot.org/help/proteome>

⁷ EBI, located at the Wellcome Genome Campus in Hinxton (UK), hosts a large number of resources of bioinformatics databases and services. SIB, located in Geneva (Switzerland), operates the ExPASy (Expert Protein Analysis System) servers, which serve as a central hub for proteomics tools and databases. PIR, hosted by the National Biomedical Research Foundation (NBRF) at the Georgetown University Medical Centre in Washington, DC (USA), is the successor to the oldest protein sequence database, Margaret Dayhoff's Atlas of Protein Sequence and Structure, first published in 1965

⁸ UniProt is supported by the National Eye Institute (NEI), National Human Genome Research Institute (NHGRI), National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute (NHLBI), National Institute on Aging (NIA), National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID), National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases (NIDDK), National Institute of General Medical Sciences (NIGMS), National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH), and National Cancer Institute (NCI) of the National Institutes of Health (NIH) under grant U24HG007822. Additional support for the EMBL-EBI's involvement in UniProt comes from European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL) core funds, the Alzheimer's Research UK (ARUK) grant ARUK-NAS2017A-1, the Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC) [BB/T010541/1] and Open Targets. UniProt activities at the SIB are additionally supported by the Swiss Federal Government through the State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation SERI. PIR's UniProt activities are also supported by the NIH grants R01GM080646, G08LM010720, and P20GM103446, and the National Science Foundation (NSF) grant DBI-1062520.

⁹ See Section 3.2 Costs for further details.

Figure 2 Roots to UniProt and its current developments

Source: Authors' elaboration on information provided by UniProt consortium **Note:** In 1984, the University of Geneva received the Atlas of Protein Sequence and Structure from NBRF, which is currently known as PIR, and started curating the first release of Swiss-Prot (1986). In 1998, the Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics was created. Until 2001, EMBL-EBI and SIB together curated Swiss-Prot and TrEMBL (Translated EMBL Nucleotide Sequence Data Library, established in 1996 because sequence data was being generated at a pace that exceeded Swiss-Prot's ability to keep up and most data had not been experimentally characterised) as a form of collaboration between the two institutes, while PIR produced the Protein Sequence Database (PIR-PSD). These data sets coexisted with different protein sequence coverage and annotation priorities. After the launch of UniProt in 2002, PIR maintained the PIR-PSD and related databases, including iProClass, a database of protein sequences and curated families, while the other resources were officially merged to originate the core resource of the consortium, UniProtKB.

UniProt is not the only protein database in the world; there are other similar databases in the US with which UniProt collaborates. One such example is RefSeq, the NCBI Reference Sequence Database¹⁰, which provides an integrated, non-redundant, and well-annotated collection of reference sequences for genomes, transcripts, and proteins. What distinguishes UniProt and makes it a unique resource are the following features:

- **Integration, standardisation, and up-to-date information.** UniProt effectively standardises and integrates a vast amount of data from multiple sources, ensuring it is continuously updated. Each protein entry in the database is linked to a tag classification, enabling users to easily recognise the various names associated with that protein in scientific literature. The scientific community actively participates in enhancing the information included in the database by submitting corrections, updates, and

¹⁰ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/refseq/>

annotations. To preserve the database's integrity, curators quickly review these contributions to verify their accuracy and correctly link them to the appropriate entries.

- **Interoperability.** UniProt data can integrate and work with a variety of other biological databases, software tools, and bioinformatics resources. Its standardised data format and protocols enable the effective exchange and share protein information with different systems, allowing the combination and cross-reference of UniProt data with other platforms. For instance, UniProtKB users can link out to 183 other resources (UniProt Consortium 2023). This feature also translates into a high level of credibility and trustworthiness among researchers and professionals.
- **Manual annotation and expert curation.** The expert curation process is particularly time-intensive and is at the heart of UniProt's distinctiveness. Experts conduct extensive and meticulous curations, which involve selecting, reviewing, and annotating data from scientific publications. In fact, despite the vast number of papers published annually, only 2-3% of those indexed in PubMed are relevant for UniProt curation (Poux et al., 2017), highlighting the careful selection required. For this reason, single researchers or organisations would not be able to achieve the same quality by manually annotating the protein sequences.

1.2. Using UniProt: how, who and for what

UniProt is accessible through its website, with data freely available for download and consultation without the need for user registration. FAIR principles guide UniProt data (Wilkinson et al. 2016), and in line with Open Science principles, UniProt guarantees a high level of openness to its resources, allowing any person to access all the databases without barriers. For instance, a user survey by Beagrie and Houghton (2021) highlights UniProt as the third most accessed resource among EMBL-EBI resources, following Europe PubMed Central and Ensembl, with Ensembl Genomes ranking fourth.

UniProt resources can be accessed in several ways, depending on the user's usage and expertise. The website offers a simple user interface that allows for searching proteins by choosing the database and typing the name of a protein. There are also more specific tools such as BLAST, Align, Peptide Search, and Retrieve/ID mapping for expert users¹¹. From the website, users can download data via File Transfer Protocol in the format they need; also, they can opt for the SPARQL endpoint, which is based on a query language for RDF, allowing any user to query UniProt databases and personalise queries depending on their specific needs.

¹¹ BLAST is provided for sequence similarity searching. The 'Align' tool allows to align two or more protein sequences using the Clustal Omega programme. The 'ID mapping' tool allows to submit a list of identifiers to retrieve the corresponding UniProt entries or to map them from or to an external database. The 'Peptide search' tool allows to submit short peptide sequences of at least 3 residues and find all UniProtKB sequences which have an exact match to the query sequence.

Finally, UniProt provides several application programming interfaces (APIs) to query and access its data programmatically.

UniProt enhances access to its services by offering a variety of free training opportunities through its platform. These include online courses like the UniProt Quick Tour, which introduces users to navigating the website and understanding the types of data available. Recorded webinars guide users through accessing and analysing data in UniProt, making these sessions particularly useful for students and early-career researchers. EMBL-EBI and SIB also offer on-demand training modules that allow flexible learning at one's own pace, as well as face-to-face and offsite training for a more interactive, hands-on experience.

UniProt database is used by several thousands of scientists and practitioners around the world every day, and its website records approximately 800,000 unique visitors (Lussi et al., 2023). By tracking IP addresses and IP2 locations of devices¹² over the last five years, the average number of unique visitors has been about 9 million annually (Figure 2).¹³ Notably, there was a significant increase in visits in 2020, reflecting the COVID-19 effect. United States (24%), China (16%), and India (8.5%) have been registered as the first three countries where UniProt data are used to access the website, while these figures slightly change also considering the programmatic access (Figure 3 below).

Within this framework, however, it is difficult to translate these figures into an actual number of individual users. Moreover, analysing UniProt usage going beyond the geographical distribution of UniProt users requires additional assumptions. As outlined in Annex A.1.2, we first applied a methodology developed by Beagrie and Houghton (2021) to estimate the average annual number of users. We then leveraged the results of the user survey described in Annex A.1.3 to further investigate the characteristics of the user population.¹⁴

¹² An IP address (Internet Protocol address) is a unique numerical label assigned to each device connected to a computer network that uses the Internet Protocol for communication. IP2Location is a technology that allows for identifying the geolocation of an IP. Between unique visitors and real users there might be large discrepancies. For instance, multiple users may share a single IP address (e.g., researchers from a single university), and a single user might have multiple IP addresses (e.g., when accessing from different locations, using various devices, or when their ISP uses dynamic IP allocation).

¹³ Due to legal requirement, UniProt has a data retention policy of five years.

¹⁴ The survey sample was not based on a probability sampling methodology. However, following several discussions with the UniProt consortium and through comparative analyses by country and field of work/research of respondents to geographical location of the web traffic data and previous data on publications and patents, we consider the sample distribution sufficiently robust to provide a meaningful description of the overall user population. On this basis, it is also deemed suitable for application in the cost-benefit analysis. Further details are provided in Annex A.1.3.

Figure 3 Unique visitors tracked by year

Source: Authors’ elaboration on UniProt consortium data. **Note:** Browser-unique visitors are tracked with Google Analytics, while Browser and Programmatic unique visitors are tracked by using Meter software, which tracks IP addresses and IP2 locations. The Browser data – blue line - was made available for the period 2017-2023, but for the sake of comparison, the figure shows the same years.

Figure 4 Country of unique visitors that accounts for at least 1%.

Source: Authors elaboration on UniProt consortium data. **Note:** Browser-unique visitors are tracked with Google Analytics, while Browser and Programmatic unique visitors are tracked by using Meter software, which tracks IP addresses and IP2 locations. The figure shows the average percentage share over the period 2019-2023.

As revealed by the users’ survey (see Annex 1.3), almost 70% of UniProt users work in universities (54%) or research institutions, including PhD students (13%), while one-fifth are employed in industry (20%).

Figure 5 UniProt users' professional status

Source: Authors' elaboration on users' survey data. **Note:** The figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample is composed of 273 respondents working in the academic sector, 100 in the private sector, 21 in the public sector (excluding public universities and research centres), 69 are PhD students, 32 undergraduate or graduate students, 7 work in the nonprofit sector (e.g., charities or NGOs), and 8 declared a different professional status.

These users operate in the vast and interconnected ecosystem of life science, especially in the field of bioinformatics. For instance, in healthcare, bioinformatics applications range from disease diagnostics and prevention to epidemic monitoring, personalised medicine, and the development of drugs, vaccines, and treatments. In farming and agriculture, bioinformatics deals with crop and breed development and pest and pathogen control, contributing to global food security (Martin et al., 2021). Previous studies have identified key research fields where UniProt is most frequently mentioned, specifically in the areas of biochemistry and molecular biology, biotechnology, computational biology, computer science, and genetics (The UniProt Consortium, 2015). In terms of patent filings, ELIXIR has identified that UniProt is most mentioned in the sectors of Chemistry, Human Necessities (including health, food, and environmental technologies), and Physics and Electricity.¹⁵ Consistent with fields where UniProt is often referenced in academic literature, the user survey (see Figure below) shows that most respondents from academia identify biotechnology, molecular biology, and bioinformatics as their main research areas. In the private sector, users are primarily involved in the pharmaceutical and biomedical technology industries.

¹⁵ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/impact/patents>

Figure 6 UniProt users' primary research field and sector of activity

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figures show the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The top pie shows academic workers by primary research field. The "Other" category mainly relates to biochemistry, biomedical sciences, and biological science in broader fields. The subsample size is 373 observations. The bottom pie shows workers employed in the private sector, public administration, and non-profit sector. The "other" category involves biotechnology, genetics, life science, higher education, and virology. The subsample size is 136 observations.

Respondents occupying roles outside core research roles, both within and outside academia, are primarily bioinformaticians, directors and managers, and wet lab researchers (Figure below).

Figure 7 Survey respondent by main role in their organisation

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figure shows respondents' percentage distribution mode. The subsample size of the top chart is 373 observations, while the subsample size of the bottom chart is 136 observations.

UniProt data are used for various purposes beyond purely scientific research. Based on the users' survey results (Figure 8), the most common service enabled by UniProt is conducting analysis and modelling, with 32% of respondents using a data pool that includes UniProt data and 6% relying solely on it. The second most frequent activity, reported by 26% of organisations, is the provision of databases or tools based on a data pool that contains UniProt, while 7% develop these tools based exclusively or nearly exclusively on UniProt data. Although less widespread, around 11% of organisations license databases or tools based on a data pool that includes UniProt, with less than 4% depending exclusively on it. Additionally, users develop algorithms and software made available through Open Access, with 21% employing datasets that incorporate UniProt and 4% primarily using UniProt data. The datasets that are typically part of the same data pool as UniProt tend to be Open Data, particularly in genomics

(approximately 60%) and structural biology (about 8%). Certain data types, like human-sensitive or controlled-access data, are exclusively available under restricted or paid access (Table 2). These products and services are primarily developed for research centres (28%), universities (28%), private companies (13%), and other organisations (Figure 8).

Figure 8 Services and products developed with UniProt

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figure shows respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample size is 509.

Figure 9 Final users of products and services developed with UniProt

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample size is 509.

Table 2 Types of data that are usually part of the same data pool as UniProt

	OPEN	PAID
None	2.6%	47.9%
Genomics	59.5%	15.5%
Proteomics	54.4%	20.4%
Gene expression	25.3%	13.2%
Structural biology	67.6%	17.1%
Literature	68.4%	15.3%
Metabolomics	10.4%	6.1%
Ontologies	27.7%	4.3%
Chemistry	17.1%	8.3%
Imaging	9.2%	4.9%
Systems biology	31.8%	7.3%
Human-sensitive / controlled access data	-	4.1%
Assay/drug screening data	-	8.1%
Others	4.7%	0.8%

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The table shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample size is 509.

2. UniProt impacts pathways

The free exploitation of UniProt data generates numerous effects relevant to its users (both academics and private users), a wider community of stakeholders, and the economy and society at large. The spreading of these effects undertakes different pathways, each entailing resources, activity, outputs, outcomes and later impacts. Following the impact pathway logic for Open Science described by Dekker, Karasz et al., 2023, we provide – in what follows – a description of how funding and resources made available to UniProt (**inputs**) translate into direct benefits for users (**outputs and outcomes**) and advancements (**impacts**) in science, the economy, and society.

The actual materialisation of UniProt's impact pathway also depends on **enabling factors**, which, in this case, include the long-standing tradition of curation of the individual databases that constitute UniProt, as well as the commitment of its founders to maintaining the project's openness. Enabling factors are conditions or elements that facilitate the implementation and success of the UniProt project, supporting the mechanisms through which it is expected to achieve its intended outcomes. As discussed in Section 1, what we now recognise as UniProt is rooted in around 20 years of work by researchers at SIB and EMBL-EBI who, in collaboration with PIR, began in 1984 to develop Swiss-Prot and later TrEMBL, building on the Atlas of Protein Sequence and Structure from NBRF. Without their continuous efforts prior to the establishment of the UniProt consortium, UniProt would not exist today in its current form. At the same time, the openness of the project is consistently ensured by the commitment of its diverse founders, who require UniProt—and all other ELIXIR resources—to adhere to Open Science principles.

The essential *inputs* for driving UniProt's impacts are the availability of research funding to establish and sustain its the operation, along with skilled staff and a well-established consortium to manage and coordinate these databases. These elements enable a series of activities that are fundamental to UniProt's exploitation. Such activities include the development and maintenance of UniProt data resources, the creation of tools for data users, the establishment of networks among data users and producers, the development and implementation of international standards, and the provision of training and support (e.g. through Helpdesk) for users. These activities yield specific *outputs*, such as making data open and easily accessible, integrating data into analytical tools and software, ensuring that data is equally accessible and usable by both industry and academia and achieving high integration within the life science ecosystem.

Any potential users, including those from industry and academia, can openly explore, extract, and analyse the vast array of data contained within UniProt resources, as well as benefit from the training activities offered. The exploitation of these resources generates several *short- and long-term outcomes* depending on the users and their specific applications.¹⁶ In the short term, both industry and academic users can expect improved work efficiency due to the time saved in collecting, integrating, and analysing the data needed for their research, which are all integrated within UniProt. Over time, this virtuous cycle is expected to boost innovation outputs in the industry and enhance academic productivity by reducing duplicated research efforts. For industry, UniProt's Open Data can be integrated with proprietary data, enabling companies to accelerate innovation, enhance existing products and services, or develop new ones, resulting in cost savings, increased productivity, and higher turnover. In academia, researchers use Open Biodata to generate new knowledge in life sciences, often resulting in a greater number of research outputs, including publications. Academic researchers may also collaborate with industry on new projects using Open Data, facilitating knowledge spillovers between sectors. Another long-term outcome is the creation of start-ups and spin-offs. Open Research Data present challenges in direct market utilisation due to the specialised expertise required for data manipulation, interpretation, and analysis. Consequently, new companies often emerge to bridge this gap by preparing and processing complex data. For example, Garcia et al. (2018) highlight the rise of European SMEs that base their business models on Open Data from public

¹⁶ Short- and long-term outcomes specifically related to UniProt fall within the categories of indicators developed and reported in the PathOS [Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook](#). For example, in terms of economic impact, the indicator 'cost-savings' includes short-term outcomes—such as time savings—which are also considered in the cost-benefit analysis of UniProt. Similarly, the indicator 'innovation output' encompasses what the IPL identifies as long-term outcomes, including new publications, patents, or less easily traceable innovations such as new products (see Box 5, Section 4 for concrete examples of products and services developed), as well as new start-ups generated by entrepreneurial ideas inspired by the use of UniProt resources. In a similar vein, academic impact indicators can be linked to collaboration intensity, citation impact, or research quality. On the societal side, the long-term outcome of 'increased knowledge and awareness in the general public' can be connected, for example, to uptake in education—since UniProt resources are frequently used to develop training materials—or to uptake by policymakers and in medical practice.

bioinformatics databases provided by ELIXIR.¹⁷ The global diffusion of UniProt resources in the life science ecosystem is anticipated to help address significant global challenges in science, the economy, and society (*impacts*). From an academic perspective, UniProt is expected to accelerate scientific discovery and enhance the quality and ethics of research outputs. Economically, by providing essential data that underpins the development of new products and technologies, UniProt is anticipated to increase the level of innovation within the industry. Its Open Access nature reduces barriers to entry for smaller companies and fosters a competitive environment that drives economic growth. Additionally, UniProt contributes to addressing societal and public challenges by enabling academia and industry to collaborate and advance faster in life sciences through innovation in key sectors, such as healthcare, by enhancing drug development, speeding up vaccine trials, and accelerating the early detection of diseases.

While certain elements of this Impact Pathway Logic (IPL) - such as inputs, activities, and outputs - may be directly controlled by the UniProt Consortium, others fall outside its direct control. Despite this, the consortium can still have an indirect influence through engagement with users and stakeholders. The final stage—impacts—remains beyond both the consortium's direct control and influence. However, impacts are certainly of high interest to funders, policymakers, and hence, the UniProt Consortium.

The **pathways from inputs to outputs, outcomes, and impacts** associated with UniProt can be **complex and dynamic**. They involve multiple steps and incorporate non-linear linkages, conditions, and enabling factors that all contribute to the process. When assessing these impacts, it is essential to recognise that their realisation depends on a combination of direct actions and the broader context in which these actions occur. For this reason, while the long-term outcomes are connected to users leveraging UniProt resources, they can be only partially attributed to UniProt, as additional inputs are necessary for their full realisation. For instance, in the causal chain from investing in UniProt to launching a new startup that provides data and services based on UniProt for companies in the agrifood sector, new inputs such as private investments and public funding would ultimately be needed to successfully launch the startup. The direct link between UniProt and the startup lies in the genesis of the entrepreneurial idea, which arises from individuals in the sector who identify a market gap. The same holds true for publications and patents, which require further efforts from researchers beyond simply accessing and using UniProt data. In the research process, additional data are often required, which may be obtained through other financial inputs, such as funding for research assistants or other resources. Therefore, patents and publications themselves cannot be considered direct benefits that can be compared to the costs associated with UniProt. Instead, they result

¹⁷ In particular, the case studies analysed by Garcia et al. (2018) focused on seven European SMEs, with four out of the seven relying on UniProt. The study proposed three different archetypes of companies: i) customising, which repackage, customise, and add value to existing public data resources, including software; ii) aggregating, which collect and aggregate Open Data from public resources and integrate it with proprietary data for industry clients; and iii) enabling, which specialise in supporting clients in finding the specific software tools and datasets they require.

from a broader research effort that encompasses multiple inputs and resources beyond UniProt alone. Wider and broader impacts are more complex to monitor as they materialise much further along the causal chain from the initial exploitation of UniProt resources. These impacts also involve a broader audience that extends beyond the direct users of UniProt. Consequently, tracking and attributing these wider effects is challenging, given the longer timelines and the involvement of various additional factors and stakeholders.

This case study investigates some of UniProt's impacts by integrating a CBA perspective¹⁸ with an impact pathways framework. Throughout the rest of the document, elements of the IPL will be referenced to explicitly highlight the links between the two. **The CBA was employed to specifically assess the impacts that are clearly and directly attributable to UniProt**, focusing on assessing the short-term outcomes it generates for its users, such as time and cost savings (Section 3). **The long-term outcomes are explored within a broader pathways contribution analysis**, recognising that such outcomes often involve multiple influencing factors, and a direct causal link to UniProt cannot always be established. Specifically, UniProt's long-term outcomes were tracked through patent and publications analyses, while other outcomes, such as the emergence of startups, are identified through more qualitative sources of evidence like interviews and user surveys (Section 4).

¹⁸ The cost-benefit analysis adopts a micro-economic perspective. This means that indirect (i.e. on secondary markets) and wider effects (e.g. induced impacts or effects on other categories of stakeholders, or economies) are often excluded from the analysis. The choice is to avoid that the analysis relies on assumptions whose reliability is difficult to check as well as any risk of double counting.

Figure 10 UniProt Impact Pathway Logic

Source: Authors

Source: Authors' elaboration. Note: The scope of the CBA is highlighted in red to mark a difference between the benefits entirely triggered by using UniProt and benefits beyond those captured by the CBA, such as the long-term outcomes highlighted in blue.

3. Cost-Benefit Analysis

The cost-benefit analysis (CBA) has been used to assess the short-term outcomes – as illustrated in the IPL for UniProt – generated by using UniProt resources on a specific group of stakeholders, such as its users, focusing particularly on measurable effects.

The analysis was guided by the CBA framework specifically tailored to the assessment of Open Science by Delugas et al. (2023). Although this framework proposes a full-fledged CBA to determine the net present value¹⁹ of an Open Resource, conducting such an analysis was not feasible for UniProt. Challenges arose in reconstructing the costs associated with the setup phase of UniProt (years 2001-2002) and the operational costs (OPEX) prior to 2017 (as explained in Section 3.2.1 below). Consequently, the analysis focused on the period from 2017 to 2023, during which reliable data were available. Despite these limitations, the CBA approach was employed to evaluate whether the benefits of UniProt outweigh the costs of its operation over this period. This comparison highlighted the 'net' benefits that UniProt provides to its users.

The figure below provides an overview of the types of costs (mostly referred to as the input “funding” in the IPL, see Section 2) and benefits (described as short-term outcome “cost savings in the IPL, see Section 2), which were identified for UniProt. Nevertheless, before diving into the specific costs (Section 3.2) and benefits (Section 3.3) associated with UniProt, along with the results of this assessment, a brief overview of the key assumptions underlying the analysis is provided below.

Figure 11 Costs and benefits of UniProt in a nutshell

Source: Authors

¹⁹ The net present value refers to the discounted value of all estimated benefits, net of the costs, of a project over a specified period.

Note: OPEX refers to operational costs. The items highlighted in red in the Figure have not been included in the CBA calculation. Information regarding setup costs was missing, while different assumptions were made for training and access costs (users' costs). The reasons are detailed in section 3.2 below.

3.1. Setting the analysis

The elements of the causal chain illustrated in the IPL require a thorough discussion in order to be translated into CBA elements. To ensure a comprehensive and relevant analysis of the costs and benefits of UniProt, discussions of the following aspects were considered:

- legal and functional boundaries of UniProt;
- the counterfactual scenario (What if UniProt did not exist?);
- the population of users affected by the costs and benefits associated with UniProt.

Although these are common issues in a CBA analysis, their treatment is not straightforward when assessing an Open Science resource like UniProt, which is indeed a knowledge-based Open Resource building on pre-existing datasets. Some methodological assumptions were needed to frame the analysis effectively, drawing on discussions with the UniProt consortium and insights gathered from user surveys, interviews and focus groups. These assumptions are briefly outlined in what follows.

3.1.1. Scope of the analysis

As shown in the IPL (Section 2), UniProt researchers engage in activities such as data curation, tool development for data users, network building among data producers and users, as well as training and support. These efforts result in several outputs, including open and integrated databases that provide extensive protein sequences and functional information, all open and accessible through the UniProt website. However, openness is not the only inherent feature of UniProt; other characteristics can be identified. UniProt databases build upon pre-existing datasets and are tightly linked to over 150 external databases, which often also link back to UniProt. The protein sequences available in UniProt come from various external institutional repositories and contributions from the broader UniProt community. In other words, UniProt's Open Resources are seamlessly integrated with existing databases within the biodata ecosystem. The primary role of UniProt researchers is to assign identification numbers, store data, and curate manual annotations to enhance data quality. While UniProt's contributions are well-defined, it is crucial to identify the scope of the CBA.

As a first step, a clear delineation of the UniProt boundaries, in legal and functional terms, is needed to accurately identify the associated costs and benefits. While determining the legal boundaries is relatively straightforward and aligns with the UniProt consortium, defining the functional boundaries is far more complex, given such an integrated ecosystem of biodata.

The main difficulty lies in distinguishing where UniProt's costs and benefits end and those of other platforms or the external researchers and institutions that generate the underlying data begin. This is a common issue with Open Resources, especially in the biosciences, where data is continuously exchanged, integrated, and enhanced by various contributors from different sources.²⁰ The added value comes through curation, annotation, and the collaborative effort that extends beyond the platform itself.

One might consider partially including the cost of research outputs developed in external linked sources and shared by UniProt as part of the benefit attributed to UniProt. However, extending the project's boundaries beyond the UniProt Consortium would not be appropriate, as most of the research shared on UniProt would have been produced regardless and is available in other databases anyway. **The unique value of UniProt lies not in the mere sharing of original research data but in its ability to integrate this data into a cohesive ecosystem that supports further scientific discovery.** This integration process, facilitated by the curation and annotation performed by UniProt researchers, is where the true benefits emerge.

Therefore, for the purpose of our assessment, in addition to resources provided by the UniProt consortium, we considered only the activities of the UniProt broader community, such as the time and effort spent by users to submit updates, corrections, and enhancements to the data functionally related to the database. These contributions add significant value and are considered part of UniProt's broader ecosystem (as discussed in Section 3.2 on costs), even though they originate from outside the UniProt consortium.

3.1.2. The counterfactual scenario

Following the CBA perspective, the analysis was addressed to compare the benefits obtained from the exploitation of UniProt with its costs by using **an incremental approach**. This entailed **a comparison between two different scenarios: one having UniProt and the other one where UniProt does not exist** (known as the counterfactual scenario)²¹. This approach enabled us to pinpoint the 'net' benefits generated by UniProt. In the context of UniProt and, more broadly, when evaluating knowledge-based Open Resources, determining what would have occurred in the absence of such resources is not straightforward. At first glance, one might think that a paid or Open Access resource offering similar data could serve as a counterfactual since UniProt primarily acts as a repository for pre-existing information. However, evidence gathered from user surveys, interviews, and focus groups (see Box 2 below) indicates that these alternatives—whether paid or Open Access— typically offer only fragmented pieces of information. Collecting and recreating the entire set of data would require a significant amount

²⁰ These inherent characteristics of Open Biodata resources can be more broadly understood within the framework of the governance of digital knowledge commons (Frischmann, Madison, and Strandburg, 2014; Hess and Ostrom, 2011; Ostrom, 1990).

²¹ See Florio 2014 and 2019, Delugas et al 2023 for a more detailed discussion on the concept of counterfactual.

of time and effort (bearable only by large institutions, not individual users) and would still not achieve the same quality and level of detail offered by UniProt.

Box 2 What if UniProt did not exist?

Survey results revealed that it is not credible to assume a unique and fully comparable alternative to UniProt. This is because the choice of alternative heavily depends on factors such as the field of research, specific projects, organisational context, etc.

As illustrated in the figure below, only a small percentage (8%) of UniProt users surveyed indicated they would have accessed the same data through a paid, closed-source option. A modest proportion (11%) of users stated they would have been able to independently recreate and gather the same data. In contrast, over half of the respondents (53%) reported that they would have obtained the data from another Open Resource. Additionally, 37% of respondents indicated that they would not have been able to carry out their research activity without UniProt. Consistency checks on individual responses and logical flow control across the survey revealed some inconsistencies in how participants answered this question²².

This finding is further supported by semi-structured interviews and focus groups. Participants emphasised that the choice between paid or public sources is likely influenced by the funding mechanisms of institutions. Universities, which rely on grants that may be intermittent, might prefer Open Access resources or recreate data themselves from original publications. In contrast, private companies, which often have stricter time constraints but softer budget constraints, might opt to pay for access if possible.

Overall, **users agreed that there is no alternative offering the same breadth of knowledge, quality, and level of integration as UniProt.**

Figure 12 Hypothetical counterfactual of UniProt

²² For example, 15% of respondents who declared they agreed with having "no alternative" also expressed agreement with an alternative to UniProt that allows them to have the same quality data, while 8% of respondents did not agree with any of the alternatives.

Note: The Figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. The alternatives were not presented as mutually exclusive. The sample size is 447. **Source:** Authors' elaboration on UniProt user survey.

Source: Authors based on survey results, interviews and focus groups

The value of UniProt, as perceived by users, lies not just in sharing protein information but in its ability to integrate protein sequences identified in the literature with an extensive body of functional information. This integration minimises redundancy and enhances connectivity with other databases, significantly increasing the utility of UniProt. It organises and refines protein data, annotates individual protein sequences, and links fragmented literature sources. For instance, the tag classification of a protein allows users to immediately identify the different names associated with that protein in the literature, while PubMed references within UniProt provide instant access to relevant background literature across various fields. Also, UniProt provides manual annotations to sequences that are considered original contributions that are not available elsewhere. These annotations result from the intensive work of UniProt researchers in collaboration with external research groups, achieving a quality that is difficult for individual users or even single institutions—whether private or public—to match.

Consequently, **meaningful comparisons regarding the implications of UniProt's absence should only be made with platforms that offer a similar level of integration.** Otherwise, the counterfactual scenario would reflect only a fraction of UniProt's capabilities. **Based on the evidence collected, it was assumed** that for the purpose of this analysis, **no single alternative** (whether closed/paid or recreating the resources) **provides the same level of integration and detail as UniProt.** The counterfactual scenario depends on the specific information users seek and consists of a combination of these alternatives. In this sense, **the results of the CBA indicate the net benefit of using UniProt compared to relying on multiple resources**, without specific implications for the use of a particular set of UniProt data available in closed form or openly provided by a different source, which would require a different analytical setup.

3.1.3. Users' population

While the IPL treats the UniProt user population as an implicit component of the causal chain, it is a key element in the CBA, as users are directly affected by the impacts arising from the use of this resource. The IPL primarily highlights the various spheres of impact—academic, economic, and societal—within which UniProt users operate. In the following discussion, we examine the challenges inherent in identifying UniProt users, particularly given its status as an Open Resource.

UniProt is an Open Database, and as typically occurs for Open Resources, its usage is monitored by tracking the web traffic and recording the number of unique visitors (unique IP addresses) visiting UniProt databases, as outlined in Section 1.2. However, as largely discussed in the literature (e.g., Ross et al. 2024; Beagrie and Houghton 2021, 2016; Fomitchev, 2010), there can be significant discrepancies between unique visitor counts and actual users over time. For instance, multiple users may share a single IP address (e.g., researchers from a single university), and a single user might have multiple IP addresses (e.g., when accessing from different locations, using various devices, or when their ISP uses dynamic IP allocation). Additionally, the unique visitor counts can include automated activities from robots or spiders. This distortion has implications for the CBA, complicating the task of determining how many users actually benefit from UniProt. To address this issue, we adapted the methodology proposed by Beagrie and Houghton (2021) to estimate the number of users of EMBL-EBI resources. The details of the assumptions and calculations we used to estimate the number of UniProt users are outlined in Annex 1.2.

Our calculations lead to an average number of users per year of about **107,000 in the period 2017-2023**.²³ Based on these estimates, we further divided the user population potentially affected by UniProt's benefits into two groups: academics and private-sector users. This division allows for more detailed considerations regarding the value of benefits accruing to these two different profiles. To estimate the number of users in each group, we relied on the survey results and assumed that approximately 67% of the total user population consists of academics, while around 20% are from private companies. Given the short timeframe of the analysis, these proportions are assumed to remain constant.

²³ Following the approach of Beagrie and Houghton (2021; 2016), our user estimate accounts for approximately 5% of the total number of researchers in the life sciences—representing the potential user base of UniProt—and should therefore be interpreted as a lower-bound estimate. See Annex 1.2 for further details.

Figure 13 UniProt users by profiles

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt consortium data and UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figure shows the estimated number of users by year over the period 2017-2023. The academic sector includes both workers and PhD students. Private users account for respondents working in the private sector. The difference between the total users and the sum of the users in the subsample includes workers from the public sector (excluding universities and research institutes that fall within the academic sector), non-profit sector workers, and a share of other workers that do not fit perfectly into the other categories. Within the category of primary users, undergraduate and graduate students, who account for 6% of the total, according to the survey results, have been excluded. This choice was made after considering the many assumptions required to model their use of UniProt resources to obtain a robust estimation of their benefits.

It is important to note that the estimated number of users may not accurately reflect the entire population accessing information provided by UniProt. The estimates represent the primary users of UniProt—those who can be directly traced through access to the resource. As an Open Resource, UniProt encompasses a variety of secondary users who can be challenging to track. These secondary users may consist of two types:

- *Cross-Referenced Users:* those who benefit from UniProt data that are incorporated into other free and open repositories (cross-references). For instance, UniProt supplies data to the Gene Ontology, which collects UniProt GO annotations and disseminates them to numerous downstream users. In return, UniProt integrates the Gene Ontology and annotations produced by other GO Consortium members. This reciprocal exchange of data is crucial for the advancement of biomedical science, as the entire ecosystem depends on data sharing and reuse. For cost-benefit analysis purposes, these secondary users are considered balanced or "cancelled out" by reciprocal inputs.
- *Dependent Users:* those who access services provided by the primary users accessing UniProt database resources. Unlike the first type of secondary user, benefits accruing to these individuals are incremental and not balanced by reciprocal input. Although efforts

were made to trace these secondary users through interviews and surveys, ²⁴ obtaining a complete picture is impractical due to the large number of primary users globally. In the context of the cost-benefit analysis, this means that our estimation achieves only a lower-bound estimation of the total UniProt user population, which can be identified as the primary layer. Additional qualitative considerations about these secondary users are discussed in Section 4 and explored through other methodologies.

3.2. Costs

Following the IPL framework, one might assume that the costs in the UniProt CBA refer solely to what is labelled as “funding” under the input category. While this constitutes a significant portion, identifying all the costs associated with an Open Resource like UniProt necessitates careful consideration due to the involvement of multiple stakeholders in putting efforts into maintaining the quality of the resources.

The UniProt ecosystem includes not only the consortium that manages the databases—referred to as the “provider” in the CBA terminology—but also a vast community of users and the scientific community that contributes data, annotations, and updates, which are subsequently shared and integrated into UniProt. In line with Delugas et al. (2023) and Catalano (2024), we considered both the costs incurred by the provider, the UniProt consortium, and those incurred by the users.

Regarding the provider costs (i.e. the “funding” reported as input in the IPL), as in any traditional CBA, we categorised them into setup costs and operational costs. Setup costs refer to the initial expenses associated with planning, designing, and launching UniProt—essentially everything required to get it off the ground. In contrast, operational costs encompass all expenditures linked to activities such as curating data, integrating annotations, adding supplementary information to the protein sequences obtained from original sources, maintaining the website, and executing all activities that allow UniProt to remain functional and up to date. All the figures related to the provider costs were made available by the UniProt Consortium, which provided all the balance sheet data they could retrieve.

The costs incurred by users, which are not explicitly stated in the IPL and arise in the process of using UniProt’s outputs, encompass the time spent acquiring the necessary skills to use UniProt’s databases, accessing and working with data, and contributing to its content by submitting updates or corrections. These costs were instead estimated by assigning a monetary value to the time users invested using UniProt and providing updates and corrections based on their responses in the user survey.

²⁴ According to the user survey, about 50% of respondents indicated that they share processed data, software or tools based entirely or partially on information gathered from UniProt with secondary users.

The Table below provides an overview of the different types of costs attributed to both the UniProt consortium and users. More details about these costs and the approach used to measure them are provided in Sections 3.2.1 and 3.2.2, respectively.

Table 3 Costs related to UniProt

STAKEHOLDER INVOLVED	COST TYPE	CATEGORY	SOURCE
Provider	Setup	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Salaries Office Equipment Legal Overheads 	These costs were not available
Provider	Operational cost (outlays and in-kind)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Salaries Travel Equipment Consumables and publications Overheads 	Balance sheet of UniProt
Users	Training costs	It refers to the time spent learning how to use UniProt and become an efficient user. Examples include learning how to navigate the UniProt website, how to exploit programmatic access and related code, and understanding which databases contain the information needed.	Estimated on the basis of data provided by UniProt consortium on training participation, evidence collected through the user survey and secondary data on salaries and hours worked by country and sector.
Users	Access costs	It refers to the time spent in using and working with UniProt resources	Estimated on the basis of evidence collected through the user survey and secondary data on salaries and hours worked by country and sector.
Users	Community contribution costs	It refers to the time spent submitting updates or corrections to UniProt entries.	Estimated on the basis of data provided by the UniProt consortium on contribution sent by year, evidence from the user survey, and secondary data on salaries and hours worked by country and sector.

Source: Authors

As described in Section 1, UniProt builds on pre-existing information held by various organisations and operates with a collaborative and interdependent approach. This interconnected nature requires careful attention when identifying the costs associated with this resource, as additional stakeholders may be involved beyond the provider and user communities mentioned earlier. For the purpose of our analysis, we carefully considered the different roles played by third parties within the UniProt ecosystem, and the following methodological choices were adopted in assessing the costs²⁵:

- Past costs related to the datasets on which UniProt was built are considered sunk costs²⁶. These costs represent investments that would have been made regardless of UniProt's data hosting and sharing activities.
- The current costs incurred by researchers and institutions to carry out and publish scientific studies – from which UniProt takes data – are considered sunk costs. While these costs are essential for creating the data that UniProt curates and integrates, they are not part of the UniProt consortium's direct financial responsibilities. Researchers would still conduct their studies independently of UniProt, meaning these costs would have been incurred regardless of the existence of UniProt itself.
- The costs associated with feeding, developing, and maintaining the external databases cross-referenced by UniProt are also treated as sunk costs. While one might argue that the benefits derived from these cross-references are not fully accounted for on the cost side, attempting to precisely estimate these expenditures based on rough data could introduce even greater bias. Treating these costs as sunk is seen as a more reliable approach, given that data sharing between UniProt and external databases is reciprocal.

Therefore, the costs included in the CBA analysis are limited to those explicitly recorded in the accounting sheets of the UniProt consortium and the costs attributable to the user community that contributes to UniProt with updates and annotation.

3.2.1. Provider costs

UniProt Consortium incurs two types of costs: setup costs and operational costs, which are described below.

SETUP COSTS

Setup costs refer to the expenses associated with establishing UniProt as a unified knowledge base. These include costs for office acquisition, legal fees associated with the consortium's formation, and expenses for equipment and personnel dedicated to designing the integrated platform. However, historical financial records detailing these initial expenses were either

²⁵ In line with similar assessments. See for instance Beagrie and Houghton 2016; 2021.

²⁶ A sunk cost is an expense that has already been incurred and cannot be recovered or altered by current or future actions.

incomplete or unavailable, making it challenging to accurately quantify the setup costs required to establish UniProt. It is important to note that at the time of UniProt’s foundation, the research group was already based at the EMBL-EBI headquarters and the University of Geneva, and what is now known as UniProtKB (see Section 1.1) was curated by the joint EMBL-EBI and Swiss-Prot teams. This suggests that office and equipment expenses were likely recorded as an in-kind setup contribution (the operational costs do not include any expenditures related to office expenses; see below).

OPERATIONAL COSTS

Operational costs encompass all in-kind contributions and expenditures required to run and maintain UniProt after its initial setup phase. The primary categories of these costs include salaries, travel, equipment, consumables, publications, and overheads. Challenges in reconstructing historical costs from 2003 (the first year of operation) to 2013 have arisen due to archival limitations. Estimating the value of in-kind contributions has proven particularly difficult, as these contributions can fluctuate over time and may apply to any of the cost categories (e.g., senior personnel time, IT infrastructure and related operational costs, high-spec laptops, associated hardware, and computer supplies). The proportion of in-kind contributions relative to total costs varies by category, ranging from less than 1% to fully covering the cost category. The table below shows the costs for the period 2017-2023 (reflecting the period for which data on the number of users are also available; see section 3.1.2 for details).

Table 4 UniProt operational costs

CATEGORIES	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Staff costs	11.4	11.5	11.5	9.1	9.9	10.4	9.8
Travel	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.04	0.1
Equipment	1.1	0.9	1.0	1.3	1.3	1.4	1.5
Consumables and publications	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.02	0.05
Overheads	2.4	2.2	3.1	1.9	2.1	2.3	2.0
Total Operational Costs	16.1	15.6	16.6	13.2	13.9	14.8	13.6

Source: Authors’ elaboration on UniProt Consortium balance sheets data. **Note:** Figures are expressed in 2024 EUR million and cover the period 2023-2017. Original data were provided in USD (referring year) and included both outlays and the value of in-kind contributions.

3.2.2. Users costs

User costs refer to the expenses that users incur both when learning to use UniProt and during its actual usage. Including these costs in the model is crucial to avoid overestimating the benefits users derive from the platform. These costs can be divided into three main categories:

- A. **Training costs:** Time spent learning how to use UniProt.
- B. **Accessing costs:** Time spent accessing UniProt resources, processing data, integrating it into workflows, and conducting research and work activities.
- C. **Community contribution costs:** Time dedicated to actively contributing to UniProt by submitting updates and corrections.

From a cost-benefit analysis perspective, the time invested in these activities represents an opportunity cost. While it does not involve direct financial expenditure, it reflects the value of time that could have been devoted to alternative tasks. The following sections detail how these costs were collected through the user survey and how their monetary value was estimated and incorporated into the CBA.

A. TRAINING COSTS

The first type of user cost relates to the time spent learning how to navigate and use UniProt. Users have several avenues to acquire the skills necessary for the effective use of this platform, including specific training sessions offered by UniProt, which often target particular functionalities. Additionally, some organisations provide training for new employees, while a significant portion of the learning curve is addressed through regular daily practice.

Overall, the user survey indicates that only a small percentage of users (around 10%, regardless of the training type) participate in training sessions, with these individuals often being primarily academics or students (see Box below). This suggests that formal education typically equips individuals with the skills needed to use UniProt effectively. Furthermore, nearly all respondents who have not undergone formal training reported being able to teach themselves how to navigate UniProt through a trial-and-error method using available resources. These findings from the survey were reinforced during semi-structured interviews, which revealed that professionals in the life sciences generally learn the basics during their formal education and typically do not require additional training. Instead, they experience a field-specific learning curve based on experimentation. The interviews also indicated that many job roles in informatics and big data analytics do not necessarily demand extensive prior knowledge of UniProt.

To estimate these costs, we gathered data on the time users invested in training through a survey, categorising it into three groups: (i) training sessions provided by UniProt, (ii) training conducted by the users' organisations, and (iii) hands-on practice. Additionally, to assess these costs, we needed to determine the number of users participating in these training courses. For

this purpose, we relied on data provided by UniProt, as well as information from the users' survey (see Box 3 below for details).

Box 3 Estimating training time and users

(i) Time spent in pieces of training provided by UniProt: Evidence from surveys highlights that the time spent attending the training offered by UniProt is between 30 minutes and one hour. To identify the magnitude of this cost, we relied on the share of users declaring to participate in the different training sources provided by UniProt, either in person or online (see Figure 14). These sources are online tutorials, workshops, webinars, recorded webinars, and YouTube videos.

Figure 14 Time spent per year to attend training courses provided by UniProt

Source: Authors elaborations on UniProt users' survey.

Note: The figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. Respondents were asked to answer the following question: *On average, how much time do you spend each year on online courses, webinars, etc., provided by UniProt?* The sample size is 477 and excludes undergraduate and graduate students.

Figure 15 Number of training sources attended by users provided by UniProt

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt Consortium data

(ii) Time spent in training conducted by the users' organisations: The distribution is the same as the time spent attending UniProt courses. This time investment is assumed to be a one-time occurrence per user, as, typically, organisations that deliver courses do it for newly hired

personnel. To identify the number of these users, we assume that the share of respondents declaring to have attended training at their organisation was a good approximation of the total number of new users approaching UniProt each year.

Figure 16 Time spent in training organised by user's organisations

Source: Authors elaboration on UniProt users' survey.

Note: The figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. This cost is assumed to be a one-time occurrence. Respondents were asked to answer the following questions: *Have you ever received training to use UniProt at your organisation? If yes, how long did it take to complete the training provided by your organisation?* The sample size is 37 and excludes undergraduate and graduate students.

Figure 17 Number of users attending training organised by their organisations

Source: Authors elaboration on UniProt users' survey.

Note: The number of users is obtained by considering the share of users declaring to have attended a training session in their organisation. The share corresponds to 10% of the total users (presented in Section 3.1.3 above), 8% of the total academic users, and 5% of the total private users.

(ii) Time spent in hands-on practice:

The modal distribution of responses from users indicates that the duration of hands-on practice typically ranges from 30 minutes to one hour. The number of users is assumed to be equivalent to those participating in training sessions at their organisations, as it follows the same logic that

this primarily occurs for newly hired employees.

Figure 18 Time spent in hands-on practice with UniProt

Note: The figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. Respondents were asked to answer the following question: "Based on your experience, how much hands-on practice is necessary to achieve the skills required to efficiently access and use UniProt data?" The sample size is 477 and excludes undergraduate and graduate students. **Source:** Authors elaboration on UniProt users' survey.

Source: Authors elaboration on UniProt users' survey and data from UniProt Consortium data

To express the value of the time invested in training in monetary terms, we used the salary equivalent for the time invested as a proxy, as detailed in Annex 1.4. Overall, the average annual training costs were estimated to be 66 EUR per new user. However, for the purposes of the CBA, we assumed that these costs would have been incurred in a counterfactual alternative scenario. Consequently, they are considered null in the analysis.

B. ACCESSING COSTS

The second type of user cost relates to the time spent accessing and downloading data from the UniProt platform in various ways, the time needed to integrate that data into workflows, and the time spent on work and research activities involving UniProt.

Similar to the training costs, the time invested in these tasks was collected through a user survey. The data gathered indicates that user responses are predominantly concentrated in the shortest time range, with less than 15 minutes typically required to access the data, regardless of the access method. Integration of the data takes longer; however, approximately 85% of respondents reported spending between less than 15 minutes and 1 hour on this task. In terms of working time, the survey shows a more varied distribution, with around 24% of respondents at each of the two extremes. This variation arises from the specific ways in which UniProt resources are utilised, which depend on factors such as the type of data accessed and the nature of the research being conducted. For example, usage patterns differ by field: bioinformatics tends to involve intensive data use, whereas drug development experiments vary in data requirements depending on the experiment's phase (see Figures below).

Figure 19 Time spent in accessing, integrating, and working with UniProt data

Working time spent with UniProt data in a week

Source: Authors elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The top chart shows the distribution mode of respondents for a single access, while the bottom chart refers to the time spent in a week. Users' respondents were asked to answer the following question: How long does it take to (i) access the most frequently used UniProt resources, considering the average time for one access; (ii) process the data gathered and integrate it into the workflow, also considering the average time for one access; and (iii) work with the most commonly used resources, based on the average time spent over a week of work. The sample size is 477 and excludes undergraduate and graduate students.

To express the value of the time invested in accessing and using UniProt in monetary terms, we used the salary equivalent for the time spent as a proxy, as outlined in Annex 1. Overall, these costs were estimated to be 23 EUR per user per access and 32 EUR per user per week. For the

purposes of our analysis, this cost was not empirically computed because it has already been incorporated into the time savings calculated from the benefit side²⁷.

C. COMMUNITY CONTRIBUTION COST

Community contribution costs refer to the time and effort users invest in maintaining, improving, or enhancing UniProt resources. From a CBA perspective, even though community contributions are voluntary, they require a certain level of effort, expertise, and resources from users that could have been allocated to other tasks. Therefore, these costs are considered an opportunity cost. They are not limited to the initial phase of using UniProt, as they occur throughout its usage. Consequently, they are classified as operating costs linked to the maintenance of UniProt resources and their continuous updates.

Similar to the training and accessing costs, evidence of community contribution costs has been gathered from user surveys. Responses indicate that the time spent submitting an update or correction to UniProt is typically less than 15 minutes.

Figure 20 Time spent on average to submit an update or a correction to UniProt

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. Respondents were asked to answer the following questions: *Have you ever submitted any updates or corrections to UniProt data? If yes, how long does it take to prepare and submit the update or correction? Please refer to the average time if you are a regular submitter; otherwise, think of the last time you did it.* The sample size is 77, which corresponds to approximately 16% of the respondents declaring that they have contributed at least occasionally to UniProt by sending updates or corrections. Undergraduate and graduate students are excluded.

²⁷ The benefits associated with UniProt (see Section 3.3) are estimated based on time savings, which must be offset by the time each user spends using UniProt to derive the "net" time savings. When conducting the CBA for resources like UniProt, it is essential to include the time spent using the resource as a user cost in the model, as omitting this could result in an overestimation of time savings. In our case, the empirical model does not account for this time because the user survey directly gathered estimates of how much additional time users would require with a hypothetical alternative to UniProt. As a result, the time savings were already reflected in the survey responses.

The number of annotations, protein sequences, and updates/corrections submitted were provided by the UniProt Consortium (see Figure below). Survey results indicate that the contribution rates vary among different user groups: while academic users represent nearly 69% of those who reported submitting at least one contribution, only 22% come from the private sector. This disparity in contribution rates can be attributed to several factors, including the time constraints or non-disclosure issues faced by private sector workers, as well as the greater propensity for patenting within the private sector.

Figure 21 Number of community contributions by year

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt Consortium data. **Note:** The figure corresponds to the total number of annotations, protein sequences, updates, and corrections sent by users.

On average, users spend slightly less than one hour to submit a contribution to UniProt, which is estimated to have a monetary value of approximately 28 EUR per contribution. The total annual cost of these community contributions was calculated by multiplying the value of a single contribution by the total number of contributions made each year. For the entire user population, the average annual cost of community contributions is approximately EUR 7,000. When breaking this down further, the cost for users in the private sector is about EUR 1,000 per year, while for those in the academic sector, it is around EUR 4,000 per year.

3.3. Benefits

As discussed in Section 2, a closer examination of the outcomes and impacts detailed in the IPL of UniProt, only **the short-term outcomes are measured with a cost-benefit analysis approach**. These **primarily consist of efficiency gains**, such as the time saved by users in collecting, integrating, and analysing the data needed for their research. In line with the CBA Open Science framework described by Delugas et al. (2023), we identified three types of efficiency gains associated with UniProt:

- the time saved in carrying out negotiations to access the Open Resources as compared to a closed alternative (transaction cost savings)
- the time saved in accessing the integrated and harmonised information within UniProt as compared to accessing individual information sources (access cost savings)
- the time saved in streamlining daily research and work activities as compared to a situation where additional work of integration should be carried out by individual users (labour cost savings).

Following Delugas et al. (2023), another potential short-term outcome is a saving in data storage costs. These savings refer to the costs avoided by users due to the free access to UniProt, eliminating the need to store data locally or on other systems. In the case of UniProt users, the benefit was considered too marginal for several reasons. Firstly, it is a company-level benefit that might become infinitesimal when attributed to a single worker since it is potentially shared by all users of the company. In fact, the avoided cost of the local storing of data would be proportional to the share of space otherwise occupied by UniProt, and according to interviews, it often represents around 5–10% of the total data stored. Secondly, it would materialise either when users only consult the UniProt website—which is extremely rare and would represent a very small saving in terms of avoided data storage—or when users entirely rely on APIs to access and use the UniProt data, meaning they do not need to store anything²⁸.

To incorporate these efficiency gains in the cost-benefit analysis, we used the value of the stated time savings from the survey as a proxy for the efficiency gains experienced by users. We also considered alternative estimation methods, such as the avoided costs method and willingness to pay through a contingent valuation survey, but we found them impractical for the assessment of UniProt²⁹. The approach of monetising the time saved by users was found to align better with the unique characteristics of UniProt as well as with the approaches used in similar studies (Beagrie and Houghton 2021; Sweeney et al. 2017; Sullivan et al. 2017; Beagrie

²⁸ According to the user survey, the majority of respondents (51%) indicated that their companies use a local system for data storage. Under the 'other' category fell a smaller fraction using a mixed system that combines both their own cloud solutions and locally stored data and those users entirely relying on APIs for their data processing and analyses. The cost savings would involve only the very small fraction of UniProt users. However, according to interviews, the API business model is not without costs, since the company would need personnel to develop and maintain the system (hardware and software), which might result in costs much higher than the savings generated by avoiding paying for cloud services or maintaining local data storage.

²⁹ Applying the avoided costs method would require information on the market price of an alternative to UniProt. However, this methodology was not feasible due to a number of several reasons. First, there is no a unique alternative to UniProt (see Section 3.1.2 for more details). Additionally, there is a scarcity of information regarding (any) fragmented alternatives that do exist. Conducting a contingent valuation survey to gather users' willingness to pay was deemed infeasible, as it may not produce robust results in this particular case. Indeed, eliciting stated preferences must follow a strict and complex protocol to be considered reliable (Johnston et al. 2017). In this instance, randomising a representative sample of users was not possible due to the unknown size of the actual UniProt user population, as there is a lack of tracking. Furthermore, accurately capturing true preferences through contingent valuation necessitates a realistic hypothetical context, an assumption that does not hold true since Open Science is a foundational principle of UniProt.

and Houghton 2014). Overall, it is a widely accepted and straightforward approach for evaluating benefits within the context of cost-benefit analysis (e.g. transport sector).

The application of this approach involved three main steps (see Annex 1 for more details):

1. Estimating the time saved: We assessed the amount of time saved concerning transactions, access, and labour activities compared to alternatives. This information was gathered from the users' survey³⁰.
2. Estimating the value of time: We differentiated the value of time based on the roles and countries of users. Data on yearly salaries was retrieved from sources like Payscale, Glassdoor, and the Economic Research Institute.³¹ They were converted into hourly rates using Eurostat and OECD statistics on weekly hours worked by sector of activity.³²
3. Estimating the benefits: After calculating the average hourly salaries per role, weighted by country, we multiplied the average hourly salary by the estimated time savings to determine the overall benefits.

In the section below, we provide a more detailed explanation of the rationale for including these efficiency gains in our analysis, along with the results of their estimation.

3.3.1. Transaction cost savings

When accessing UniProt resources, users are not required to create an account, nor do they need to engage in discussions about usage types or organisational needs before accessing the data. UniProt's data adheres to FAIR principles and allows for various methods of utilisation, making the data adaptable across multiple fields within the life sciences ecosystem. This openness significantly reduces the time users would typically spend navigating copyright agreements, conducting ad-hoc negotiations for access to specific data, or managing other research-related protocols. As a result, the opportunity cost associated with this saved time translates into the first short-term outcome generated due to using UniProt resources, namely transaction cost savings for users.

³⁰ Respondents to the survey were asked to answer the following question: How much additional time you would have needed in a week for i) making ad-hoc agreements to be allowed to access the data from another entity; ii) finding, accessing the data (and/or tools with equivalent functionality) from another open source and integrating them within the workflow; iii) finding, accessing the data (and/or tools with equivalent functionality) from a paid source and integrating them within the workflow; and iv) recreating the data, yourself / your team; v) performing the work or research tasks in a week without UniProt.

³¹ The social cost of labour is typically distinct from observed salaries. Actual wages can be biased due to distortions in labour and product markets, such as the presence of minimum wages, high unemployment rates, and the existence of informal or illegal sectors. However, for skilled and highly skilled workers who have previously been engaged in similar activities, the shadow wage can often be assumed to be equal to or close to the market wage (EC 2014).

³² Specifically, the country average was employed for the private sector, while public sector and academic sector worked hours were used to calculate the hourly salary of users working in these sectors. All currencies were converted in 2024 EUR prices.

Evidence from the user survey shows that the transaction time saved varies based on the types of data accessed within UniProt, as well as user and organisational characteristics. Many respondents noted that the bargaining time could extend to weeks, if not months, depending on the context. The choices of respondents predominantly fall into three categories of times (see Figure 22): less than 1 hour, 1 to 3 hours, and more than 3 days. This distribution underscores the significant variability in transaction times. However, a substantial portion of responses was categorised as "not applicable," which emphasises the challenges users face in identifying suitable alternatives to UniProt. This finding highlights the unique role that UniProt plays in providing accessible data without the lengthy negotiations typically associated with data access in other platforms.

Figure 22 Transaction time savings per week

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. Respondents were asked to answer the following question: How much additional time would you have needed in a week to make ad-hoc agreements and be allowed to access the data from another entity? The sample size is 477 and excludes undergraduate and graduate students.

The evidence gathered from users' surveys and interviews suggests the need for a cautious approach in estimating transaction cost savings. Several factors were identified that contribute to the risk of overestimating this benefit:

- This benefit is more relevant to the organisation where users are employed rather than to individual users themselves. It is unlikely that UniProt users would directly bear the cost of negotiating access to a particular data repository or knowledge base. Instead, researchers primarily benefit from avoiding asking their organisation to handle the contracts required for database access, searching for potential alternatives, or completing the administrative steps in submitting a purchase request.
- Multiple users from the same organisation would share this benefit. Therefore, attributing the full benefit to every UniProt user might lead to an inflated estimate of the number of individuals experiencing this efficiency gain.
- The exact number of potential alternatives that each user might need to negotiate with remains uncertain.

- The effort involved in negotiations is generally time-consuming the first time an organisation engages with a new database or platform. However, this effort tends to diminish over time, as processes like automatic renewals often reduce the need for repeated negotiations.

To ensure accuracy and avoid overestimation, we based our calculation on the following assumptions:

- The time saved has been monetised for all new users and across subsamples of new users accessing UniProt.³³
- The benefit generated during one week of work is considered to represent the time saved from negotiating a single UniProt alternative.
- The benchmark for the time spent in a year negotiating a single alternative is assumed to be one full week of work.
- The benefit is applied to a single alternative per new user.

Based on these assumptions, transaction cost savings are measured as the time saved over a year by avoiding negotiations for accessing a single UniProt alternative, which equates to approximately one week of work. For all new users, the average time savings attributed to avoiding these negotiations amounts to about 5.6 hours per new user each year, which translates to a monetary value of 148 EUR per new user per year.

When analysing the subsamples of private and academic users, the amount of time saved remains relatively consistent across the two groups. However, the key difference lies in the value of time, which is notably higher for private-sector users. Specifically, the value of time saved for private sector users is almost 100 EUR higher than that for academic users, reflecting the generally higher salary levels in the private sector compared to academia.

Table 5 Transaction cost savings – estimation results

USER SEGMENT	HOURS SAVED / PER NEW USER	EUR / PER NEW USER	AVG N. NEW USERS	AVG ANNUAL TOTAL BENEFIT
All users	5.6	148 EUR	10,075	1,276 EUR thousand
Private sector users	6.0	210 EUR	2,113	379 EUR thousand
Academic sector users	5.4	120 EUR	7,202	741 EUR thousand

Source: Authors' elaboration of UniProt users' survey and UniProt consortium data. **Note:** All users also include individuals working in public administration, the non-profit sector, and other users. Students are excluded. The average number of users is calculated over the period 2017-2023, and the average total and per person annual benefit is calculated.

³³ The number of new users was estimated by considering the share of users declaring to have attended a training session in their organisation. The share corresponds to 10% of the total number user (presented in Section 3.1.3 above), 8% of the total academic users, and 5% of the total private users.

3.3.2. Access cost savings

As outlined in Section 1, UniProt serves as an integrated platform that consolidates extensive protein sequence and functional information from multiple sources into a comprehensive database. The short-term outcome of this process is access cost savings, which materialise from different channels. The integration eliminates the need for users to navigate through multiple databases individually, saving both time and, in many cases, subscription fees. UniProt's structured organisation further amplifies these access time savings by providing advanced search tools and user-friendly interfaces, enabling users to quickly identify specific proteins and their related data. This approach is significantly more efficient than accessing various sources with differing search functionalities. Additionally, UniProt's regular updates ensure that users always work with the most current and accurate data, reducing the burden of manually verifying the accuracy of the information. However, accurately quantifying these access cost savings requires careful consideration of the following aspects:

- Access cost savings are closely tied to the frequency of UniProt access, which gathers information and integrates the data into workflows. This is because those who access it only a few times per year might save more time per session compared to those who access it more frequently due to the differing ways they utilise UniProt. The user survey (Figure 23) found that 49% of users access UniProt weekly while 26% daily. Only a quarter of respondents indicated that they were accessing UniProt monthly or less than once per month.

Figure 23 Access frequency

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. The sample size is 477 and excludes undergraduate and graduate students.

- Not all interactions with the UniProt platform involve downloading and integrating data into research workflows. Insights from user interviews and discussions with the UniProt team responsible for monitoring web traffic indicate that users engage with UniProt in

diverse ways. Researchers access the platform for various purposes, which depend on factors like the method of accessing and storing UniProt data (e.g., downloading vs API usage), organisational policies on data update frequency (e.g., annual updates), and the specific type of information needed for their research projects. Often, the UniProt website is accessed for quick consultations to obtain specific data points required for particular research tasks. Even users who have previously downloaded extensive datasets via FTP or programmatic access frequently return to the website to retrieve targeted information. This highlights that while bulk data downloads are common, users still rely on the web interface for its efficiency in providing quick, precise answers, making it a valuable resource for both routine checks and in-depth data integration.

- For frequent users, distinguishing between access cost savings and labour cost savings (see Section 3.2.2) can be challenging. By definition, these users regularly engage with UniProt and frequently consult the website for their research needs. As a result, they may find it difficult to clearly differentiate between the time saved in accessing data and the time saved in performing daily research tasks, such as gathering information from the website and integrating that data into their workflows.
- Access time savings vary based on the alternative being considered. As discussed in Section 3.1.2, no single resource serves as a perfect counterfactual to UniProt; different alternatives may exist depending on the specific information the user is seeking. Survey results reveal that when comparing access to UniProt with the alternative of "recreating the data," the largest time savings are reported, with approximately 40% of respondents indicating that this would save them at least one day per week. In contrast, when comparing UniProt with an "Open Access resource," around 47% of respondents estimate savings of less than three hours. Additionally, a significant portion of respondents (about 38-39%) selected "not applicable" for both paid resources and the option of recreating the data.

Figure 24 Access time savings per week by alternative

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. The sample size is 477 and excludes undergraduate and graduate students. Respondents were asked to answer the following question: *how much additional time would you have needed in a working week for i) finding, accessing the data (and/or tools with equivalent functionality) from another open source and integrating them within the workflow; ii) finding, accessing the data (and/or tools with equivalent functionality) from a paid source and integrating them within the workflow; and iii) recreating the data, yourself / your team (Please consider only the time strictly necessary to collect and reconstruct the data in the same format you access UniProt resources).*

To ensure accuracy and avoid overestimation, we based our calculation on the following assumptions:

- Access time savings are monetised by weighting the value of time against the frequency of access, recognising that access frequency may vary based on the user's professional role.
- To avoid double counting benefits already included under labour cost savings (see Section 3.3.3), we assign a zero value to users who access the platform weekly or daily. For users who access UniProt monthly or less frequently, the weekly access savings are multiplied by a frequency factor corresponding to the number of weeks during which the benefit is realised.

The results of the time-savings monetisation are reported in Table 6. On average, UniProt saves users approximately six hours per week, which is 176 EUR per week. A user accessing UniProt monthly saves 2,115 EUR per year, while those accessing a few times per year save 529 EUR. The average value of the benefit is higher for those working in the private sector (246 EUR per week) compared to those working in the academic sector (149 EUR per week).

Table 6 Access cost savings – estimation results

	HOURS SAVED PER WEEK	EUR PER PERSON	AVERAGE ANNUAL BENEFIT PER PERSON		AVERAGE N. USERS	AVERAGE TOTAL BENEFIT
			ACCESS MONTHLY	ACCESS LESS THAN ONCE PER MONTH		
All users	6.8	176.3 EUR	2,115 EUR	529 EUR	25,567	39.87 EUR million
Private sector users	6.7	245.6 EUR	2,948 EUR	737 EUR	5,647	12.82 EUR million
Academic sector users	6.8	149.6 EUR	1,795 EUR	449 EUR	17,285	22.91 EUR million

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey and unique visitors user data provided by the UniProt consortium. **Note:** All users also include individuals working in public administration, the non-profit sector, and other users. Students are excluded. The average number of users is calculated over the period 2017-2023, and the average total and per person annual benefit is calculated.

3.3.3. Labour cost savings

The last short-term outcome generated by using UniProt is saving in labour costs. This arises from various daily activities related to conducting work and research tasks. UniProt helps researchers by reducing the time spent interpreting data and cross-referencing multiple sources. By minimising redundancy and providing a unified view of protein information, UniProt enables users to avoid the duplication of efforts often required to reconcile conflicting data from different databases. UniProt includes references to PubMed and other scientific literature, allowing users to access background information and research articles related to specific proteins without the need for further searches. The high level of integration of UniProt into the life sciences ecosystem ensures a high degree of reliability, saving users the time required for data verification and eliminating the need to justify UniProt's credibility to clients or stakeholders.

Users' survey revealed that the most common amount of time saved in performing their work, thanks to UniProt, is more than three days of work per week (about 19%, see Figure 25).

Figure 25 Weekly labour time savings

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. The sample size is 477 and excludes undergraduate and graduate students. Respondents were asked to answer the following question: *how much additional time would you need to perform your work or research tasks in a week without UniProt?*

A key challenge in quantifying this benefit was determining the appropriate time frame to consider for each respondent. While employees generally work an average of 48 weeks per year, excluding bank holidays, time off, and weekends, assuming that all users interact with UniProt data at the same intensity year-round would likely result in an overestimation of this benefit. Interviews revealed that individuals working in data-intensive companies or research roles may spend a significant portion of their time on data analysis, management, or tasks facilitated by UniProt, such as research design or literature reviews. In contrast, other users might only utilise UniProt at the initial stages of their research design or for specific tasks that do not encompass their entire workload. Following a conservative approach, some assumptions were made on the maximum amount of time that users might spend during a year working with UniProt. We rely on additional information retrieved from the user survey, namely the time spent by respondents each week on various activities (Figure 26). UniProt users, on average, dedicate a significant share of their weekly time to data analysis and management, while activities such as literature review and software development are less frequent.

Figure 26 Distribution of respondents by weekly time across selected activities

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey. **Note:** The figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. The sample size is 477 and excludes undergraduate and graduate students.

To ensure accuracy and avoid overestimation, we based our calculation on the following assumptions:

- Two scenarios were identified based on the typology of activities. The lower bound considers time spent on data analysis and management, while the upper bound includes these activities plus literature review and software development.
- In the lower bound scenario, users are assumed to spend 13 hours per week on activities such as data analysis and management. In the upper bound scenario, this increases to 29 hours per week, including literature review and software development.
- Assuming 48 working weeks per year, this translates to approximately 16 weeks per year for lower-bound activities and 24 weeks per year for upper-bound activities. These factors are then used to calculate the labour cost savings per person per year.

Table 7 Time savings – estimation results

	HOURS SAVED PER WEEK	TOTAL HOURS SAVED PER YEAR - LOWER BOUND	TOTAL HOURS SAVED PER YEAR - UPPER BOUND	AVERAGE N. USERS (2017-2023)
All users	9	146	219	100,549
Private sector users	8	135	203	21,084
Academic sector users	10	153	229	71,879

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey and unique visitors data provided by UniProt consortium.

Note: All users also include those individuals working in public administration, the non-profit sector, and other users

who do not fall into either of the two subsamples: academia or the private sector. Students are excluded. The average number of users is calculated over the period 2017-2023.

Table 8 Labour cost savings – estimation results

	EUR/WEEK PER PERSON	ANNUAL LABOUR COST SAVING PER PERSON – LOWER BOUND	AVERAGE ANNUAL BENEFIT - LOWER BOUND	ANNUAL LABOUR COST SAVING PER PERSON – UPPER BOUND	AVERAGE ANNUAL BENEFIT- UPPER BOUND
All users	243 EUR	3,884 EUR	332.17 EUR million	5,825	524 EUR million
Private sector users	319 EUR	5,098 EUR	91.43 EUR million	7,647	144.23 EUR million
Academic sector users	189 EUR	3,031 EUR	190.03 EUR million	4,547	29.39 EUR million

Source: Authors’ elaboration on UniProt users’ survey and unique visitors data provided by UniProt consortium.

Note: The average annual benefit is calculated over the period 2017-2023.

3.4. Overall results

The Table below summarises the estimated operational costs and benefits for UniProt in a typical reference year. These are presented according to two scenarios—upper and lower bounds—which primarily differ in the calculation of labour cost savings (see Section 3.3.3).

A few important considerations arise from these results:

- Personnel costs incurred by the UniProt consortium account for a significant share (70.91%) of the expenses required to operate this resource. This highlights the unique nature of UniProt, which necessitates a larger investment in personnel.
- Labour cost savings are the most substantial of the three efficiency gains considered in this analysis, while transaction savings result in the least amount of savings and impact the smallest proportion of users. The efficiency gains from labour time savings stem from the ongoing efforts of the UniProt Consortium to enhance the accessibility of UniProt data, improve interoperability, and manually annotate the sequences contained in Swiss-Prot. This sustained effort has contributed to the high level of integration that UniProt resources now enjoy within the life sciences ecosystem. It is also closely linked to the evolving nature of such Open Resources, which have increasingly fostered collaboration and interdependence with other Open Resources over time.
- By comparing the estimated costs and benefits associated with UniProt, it is evident that the benefits significantly outweigh the costs. Specifically, each user experiences **a net benefit ranging from 3,513 EUR** (based on the lower bound estimation) **to 5,475 EUR** (upper bound estimation) in a year. However, it is crucial to interpret these results

accurately; focusing solely on operational costs when assessing benefits may lead to an underestimation of the historical costs incurred over the years. These historical investments, while currently impossible to retrieve or estimate, have played a vital role in generating the current benefits users experience.

Table 9 Overview of results for the total user population

ALL USER POPULATION	LOWER BOUND	UPPER BOUND
COSTS		
Total annual average Operational Costs	14,664,728	
<i>Total staff costs (EUR)</i>	10,403,892	
<i>Other OPEX</i>	4,260,836	
<i>Travel (EUR)</i>	135,377	
<i>Equipment (EUR)</i>	1,455,562	
<i>Consumables and publications (EUR)</i>	69,465	
<i>Overheads (EUR)</i>	2,600,433	
Total USER costs (EUR)	7,381	
<i>Community contribution costs</i>	7,381	
TOTAL COSTS	14,672,109	
BENEFITS		
<i>Transaction cost savings</i>	1,276,382	
<i>Access cost savings</i>	39,870,241	
<i>Labour cost savings</i>	332,166,024	524,000,142
TOTAL BENEFITS	373,312,647	565,146,765
TOTAL NET BENEFIT PER USER	3,567	5,475

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey and unique visitor data provided by UniProt consortium. **Note:** The table reports the average annual values calculated over the period 2023-2017. All values are expressed in 2024 EUR. For total user costs, only the value of community contribution costs was included in the analysis. As explained in Section 3.2.2, training costs were considered negligible compared to alternative scenarios, while access costs were factored into the calculation of access cost savings on the benefit side to avoid duplication and thus were excluded from the total user costs.

It is important to stress that the above results derive from valuing the benefit brought about by UniProt by means of the perceived time saved by users in transaction, accessing and labour activities. Nevertheless, an alternative perspective is to consider the time invested in learning how to use UniProt, in accessing it and in contributing to its update with submissions and corrections (presented as user costs in Section 3.2) - as a proxy of their minimum willingness to pay for such resource (revealed preference as compared to a stated preference method). Essentially, by choosing to invest their time in using UniProt, users demonstrate its value to them.

The minimum willingness to pay for UniProt, estimated using this approach, ranges from 534 EUR (in the lower bound scenario) to 770 EUR (in the upper bound scenario) per user per year.

Notably, these values vary depending on the user's profile. For private users, the willingness to pay ranges from 704 to 1,017 EUR, while for academics, it ranges from 422 to 609 EUR. These differences underscore the different value of the working time across sectors and the different composition of the population attending a large share of the training, specifically for academics, which dedicate much more time in training and submitting contributions compared to private users, although at the very beginning of their career when their salaries are much lower. These differences underscore the varying value of working time across sectors and the differing composition of the population attending a large share of the training, particularly academics, who dedicate significantly more time to training and submitting contributions compared to private sector users, even at the very beginning of their careers when their salaries are much lower. This estimation represents the minimum direct value that UniProt has for its users.

When comparing the costs incurred by users with the efficiency gains they achieve by utilising this resource, we found that the benefits exceed the costs by a factor of seven. In cost-benefit analysis terminology, this is referred to as the benefit-cost ratio³⁴ (see the Table below).

Table 10 Average user costs and benefits, user cost per person

		TOTAL AVERAGE USER COSTS	TOTAL AVERAGE USER BENEFITS	B/C RATIO	USER COST PER PERSON
All users	Lower Bound	53.7 EUR million	373.3 EUR million	7.0	534 EUR
	Upper Bound	77.4 EUR million	565.1 EUR million	7.3	770 EUR
Private users	Lower Bound	14.8 EUR million	104.6 EUR million	7.1	704 EUR
	Upper Bound	21.4 EUR million	157.4 EUR million	7.3	1017 EUR
Academic Users	Lower Bound	30.4 EUR million	213.7 EUR million	7.0	422 EUR
	Upper Bound	43.8 EUR million	316.0 EUR million	7.2	609 EUR

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey and unique visitor data provided by UniProt consortium. **Note:** The Table presents estimates of all costs incurred by users and the user benefits. The benefit-cost (B/C) ratio is calculated by dividing the "Total Average User Benefits" by the "Total Average User Costs." All values represent the average over the period from 2017 to 2023. To determine the user costs per person, we divide the total costs by the average number of users during the period considered. All values are expressed in 2024 EUR.

³⁴ Please note that the benefit-cost ratio shown in the table reflects the user's perspective, as it only considers the costs and benefits directly impacting users. In a typical social CBA analysis, this indicator is calculated by taking into account all costs and benefits, including those incurred by the provider (such as setup and operational costs). In this case, a comprehensive analysis was not possible due to the lack of information regarding the setup costs.

Evidence from the focus groups contributed to validating our results. The time savings estimated from the user survey were largely confirmed by the participants in the first focus group. The mechanism that triggers these significant time savings certainly relies on the integration of protein data with all other information. However, more importantly, it is attributable to the massive manual annotation efforts by UniProt researchers, a task that could not be accomplished by other existing organisations, even with the support of AI technologies. The second focus group was involved in a thought experiment to assess participants' willingness to pay for UniProt, resulting in a minimum consensus WTP of 1,000 EUR per user per year.

Although this quantitative amount is far from being statistically representative of the user community, the minimum amount that individuals declared they were willing to pay prompts two main reflections. Firstly, it provides us with a lower bound of the annual benefit a person might derive from using UniProt. Secondly, the participants did not emphasise a low valuation of UniProt in their reasoning. Instead, they justified their choices based on considerations of equity and fairness. They pointed out that many students rely on UniProt during their studies and would be unable to afford access if it were not freely available. Likewise, researchers from less rich countries or small companies might be unable to afford high costs, even though they would be willing to pay more. Moreover, academics often exhibit a lower WTP due to financial constraints and uncertainty regarding their research grants over time.

Our results also align with other studies investigating the socio-economic value of Open Resources. In the evaluation of three researcher data centres - Economic and Social Data Service (ESDS), the Archaeology Data Service (ADS), and the British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC) - Beagrie and Houghton (2014) show that users reported substantial improvements in research efficiency, with benefits ranging from 2 to over 20 times the cost of operating the data centres. Similarly, Beagrie and Houghton (2021) estimated that the use value of EMBL-EBI amounted to approximately EUR 6.5 billion³⁵ per annum, which is 49 times the total operational costs. Their contingent valuation stood at approximately EUR 1.5 billion³⁶ per annum, 11 times the total costs. Similarly, Technopolis (2021) reviewed the impacts of EMBL experimental services, estimating a value of around EUR 17.5 million per year. To make the magnitude of our estimation of net benefit per person more comparable, we recalculated figures based on data reported in two studies. According to Beagrie (2014), the estimated efficiency gain per active user for the three data centres ranges approximately from EUR 2 thousand to EUR 12.3

³⁵ £5.5 billion, converted with an exchange rate of GBP/EUR at 1.18 in the year 2021. retrieved from https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/procedures-guidelines-tenders/information-contractors-and-beneficiaries/exchange-rate-infoeuro_en

³⁶ £1.25 billion, converted with an exchange rate of GBP/EUR at 1.18 in the year 2021. retrieved from https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/procedures-guidelines-tenders/information-contractors-and-beneficiaries/exchange-rate-infoeuro_en

thousand.³⁷ In Beagrie (2021), the efficiency gain per user for EMBL ranges from a minimum of approximately EUR 6.7 thousand to EUR 28.8 thousand.³⁸ In Technopolis (2021), the estimated value per external user is approximately EUR 8 thousand.³⁹ Overall, this evidence strongly suggests that Open Resources generate substantial net benefits.

4. Benefits beyond CBA

As shown in the UniProt IPL, the benefits of using UniProt resources extend beyond short-term outcomes, such as the efficiency gains—like time and cost savings—measured through the CBA (Section 3). These benefits may reach further, encompassing what the IPL identifies as *long-term outcomes*, also referred to as *enablement* benefits in Delugas et al. (2023). While they are linked to the use of UniProt, their occurrence also depends on additional user effort and resources, making it challenging to attribute them solely to UniProt, unlike the short-term outcomes. Therefore, the following discussion focuses on describing the characteristics of the IPL long-term outcomes that were, to some extent, measured either quantitatively or qualitatively in the framework of this evaluation. These benefits are all tied to the generation of knowledge. Essentially, UniProt contributes to accelerating scientific research and innovation in various forms, thereby facilitating the creation of new knowledge.

To investigate the long-term outcomes of knowledge creation that can be quantitatively tracked, we carried out publication and patent analyses (Sections 4.1 and 4.2). These analyses showed how the knowledge enabled by UniProt's data contributes, at least to some extent, to the creation of new publications and innovations. To this end, we retrieved information on publications and patents that mentioned UniProt or its resources in their text. More specifically, the following keywords were searched in the titles and abstracts of academic publications published between 2003 and 2022 and in the title, abstract, description, and or claims of patent publications⁴⁰: UniProtKB, UniProt, TrEMBL, SwissProt, Swiss-Prot, UniParc, UniRef, UniRef100,

³⁷ In pound: £1.6 thousand to £9.7 thousand, converted with an exchange rate of GBP/EUR at 1.26 in the year 2014. retrieved from https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/procedures-guidelines-tenders/information-contractors-and-beneficiaries/exchange-rate-infoeuro_en This was calculated by dividing the total efficiency gains—£68 million to £112 million for ESDS (with 18,098 users), £13 million to £58 million for ADS (11,020 users), and £10 million to £58 million for BADC (5,959 users)—by their respective numbers of active users.

³⁸ In pound: £5.7 thousand to £24.4 thousand, converted with an exchange rate of GBP/EUR at 1.18 in the year 2021. retrieved from https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/procedures-guidelines-tenders/information-contractors-and-beneficiaries/exchange-rate-infoeuro_en. This was calculated considering a total of 450,000 users and total efficiency gains between £2.6 billion and £11 billion.

³⁹ The report states an average of annual external user of approximately 2,200 from academia and industry.

⁴⁰ See below for details on the timeframe used for the patent analysis.

UniRef90, and UniRef50.⁴¹ The data sources used were OpenAIRE for publications and Lens⁴² and Orbis IP⁴³ for patents.

Two approaches were used to analyse patents. The first narrowed the search to UniProt-related keywords in titles and abstracts of patents filed after the establishment of UniProt, i.e., between 2002 and 2021, while the second extended it to the full text, including descriptions and claims, of patents filed since the creation of Swiss-Prot, i.e., between 1988 and 2022. The narrower approach identified fewer patents than the extended analysis (44,747 vs 78 distinct patent families), but it highlighted the higher value of UniProt resources by focusing on cases where UniProt plays a central role in innovation. Although no causal conclusion can be drawn solely from this analysis, the explicit mention of UniProt in titles and abstracts suggests a strong reliance on its resources, reinforcing its significance in patented discoveries. For completeness, findings from both approaches are detailed in Section 4.2.1 (narrowed analysis) and Section 4.2.2 (extended analysis). Together, these analyses provide a comprehensive view of UniProt's contribution to innovation.

Finally, a segment of innovation can only be discussed qualitatively, as it remains difficult to quantify due to the absence of systematic evidence, unlike cases where innovation can be traced through new publications or the creation of patented goods and services. To this end, we gathered evidence of the most common of these *enablement* (i.e. the establishment of collaborations, contributing to the establishment of spin-offs and start-ups, and enhancing production processes) through the users' survey and interviews (Section 4.3).

4.1. Publication analysis

Between 2003 and 2022, **6,737 publications** referenced UniProt or one of its datasets in the title or abstract while the number raise up to 15,202 if the search is extended to the full text.⁴⁴ As shown in the Figure below, the number of publications has steadily grown over this period, underscoring the platform's increasing significance in scientific research. When UniProt was launched in 2003, 114 publications were published referencing UniProt. In 2022, the number of new publications referencing UniProt had risen to 515, reflecting UniProt's expanding influence

⁴¹ The list of keywords were discussed with UniProt Consortium and reflects the one previously used by EBI-EMBL to analyse UniProt's impacts. Further information are available at https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1aEmSQR9DGOIZmHALuQV9mLv7Mw9Ppkin#scrollTo=ZWtNO2K7QjS_&uniqifier=1

⁴² <https://www.lens.org/>

⁴³ <https://login.bvdinfo.com/R1/OrbisIntellectualProperty> for which CSIL has a licence.

⁴⁴ Publications referencing UniProt or one of its resources were retrieved implementing the following steps: 1) downloading the dump of OpenAIRE data (version December 2023), 2) indexing the data in an in-house ElasticSearch engine at OPIX. It consisted in lowercasing and stemming the text and organising the data based on the fields provided in the OpenAIRE dump, 3) replicating the same analysis for each search term and retrieve the results from the database.

as a trusted source of protein data. A sharp peak occurred in 2020, with 565 articles published, likely due to the surge in global scientific activity spurred by the COVID-19 pandemic, as researchers sought reliable protein data for developing treatments and vaccines. After this pandemic-driven increase, the number of publications referencing UniProt gradually returned to pre-2020 levels.

Figure 27. Number of publications referencing UniProt or one of its datasets over time (2003-2022)

Source: Authors' elaboration

Among UniProt's various databases, UniProt as a whole was the most frequently mentioned between 2003-2022, appearing in 3,601 distinct publications. Following this were Swiss-Prot, with 2,575 citations, and UniProtKB, with 1,119 mentions. In contrast, UniParc was the least referenced, with only 19 publications.⁴⁵ Notably, most publications (87.5%, or 5,893) mentioned only one database, while a smaller percentage (12.5%, or 844 publications) referenced multiple UniProt resources. Of the 844 studies that mentioned more than one database, the most frequent combinations were Swiss-Prot and UniProtKB (270 publications, 32.0%), UniProt and UniProtKB (245 publications, 29.0%), and Swiss-Prot and TrEMBL (238 publications, 28.2%), and Swiss-Prot and UniProt (210 publications, 24.9%). These combinations reflect how researchers often rely on different databases within UniProt to complement their research needs. Figure 27 shows the combination of databases mentioned together. The combination of databases mentioned together in some studies reflects the different strengths of each resource. For example, combining Swiss-Prot and UniProtKB may indicate that researchers are using Swiss-Prot for high-confidence annotations while also leveraging the broader UniProtKB for its extensive unreviewed protein data when exploring uncharted or high-throughput areas of research.

The way researchers mention UniProt databases has evolved over time (see Figure 28). Mentions of UniProt as a whole have grown, reflecting its role as a unifying platform that caters to both manual and high-throughput research. Researchers are increasingly acknowledging the integrated nature of protein data. As scientific research grows more interdisciplinary and data-

⁴⁵ Note that since in some cases the same publication mentioned more than one dataset, the number of publications by mentioned dataset might be double-counted.

driven, many prefer to reference UniProt as a comprehensive resource rather than focus on specific sub-databases, especially when the study involves large-scale data analysis across multiple datasets.

Figure 28 Combination of databases mentioned together

Source: Authors' elaboration

Conversely, Swiss-Prot citations have decreased, likely due to increased familiarity with the integrated UniProtKB, the broader resource that emerged from the merger of Swiss-Prot and TrEMBL. Additionally, this shift may also reflect changes in protein research, where large-scale,

automated data analysis has become more prevalent, favouring the more inclusive UniProtKB, which contains both reviewed (Swiss-Prot) and unreviewed (TrEMBL) entries.

Nonetheless, many researchers still choose to mention Swiss-Prot independently, likely due to its reputation for high-quality, manually curated entries. Swiss-Prot remains a go-to resource for investigations requiring manually curated data, such as studies on enzyme functionality, disease mechanisms, and protein-protein interactions. In fields requiring precise, validated data—such as structural biology or pharmacology—researchers may prioritise Swiss-Prot for its reliability, even though it is technically part of the larger UniProtKB. In other words, researchers in these areas may be cautious about relying solely on automated annotations and prefer the rigour of Swiss-Prot’s expert-reviewed content.

The minimal citations for UniParc (19 publications) likely stem from its specific use case. UniParc stores protein sequence data without annotation, making it valuable primarily for sequence tracking and database integrity rather than for immediate biological insight. This narrow use case may explain its lower citation rate compared to the more comprehensive, annotated resources such as UniProtKB and Swiss-Prot.

Figure 29 Distribution of publication by mentioned resource and year

Source: Authors’ elaboration. **Note:** Publications mentioning more than one resource are fractionalised.

Publications citing UniProt databases span a wide array of fields of science⁴⁶, including agricultural and veterinary sciences, engineering and technology, medical and health sciences, natural sciences, and even social sciences (see Figure 30). This breadth highlights UniProt’s versatility as a data source that is critical not only for life sciences but also for interdisciplinary studies where biology intersects with other domains. Given UniProt’s focus on proteins, it is

⁴⁶ The Field of Science classification is defined in the Frascati Manual (<https://unstats.un.org/wiki/download/attachments/101354089/FOS.pdf?api=v2>). Within this project, the publications mentioning UniProt, or its resources, were classified according to the Field of Science taxonomy using the SciNoBo algorithm as described in Kotitsas et al (2023).

unsurprising that the medical and health sciences represent the largest share of publications. Proteins are fundamental to understanding the molecular basis of diseases and the development of new therapies. Within this field, developmental biology is a key area as researchers investigate the roles proteins play in cell differentiation, organ formation, and tissue regeneration.

Figure 30 Distribution of Field of Science (FOS)

Source: Authors' elaboration

Out of the 6,737 publications citing UniProt, a significant proportion—1,962 publications or **30.8%**—are directly related to the **United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**⁴⁷ (see 30⁴⁸).⁴⁹ This substantial share highlights the growing recognition of protein data's crucial role in addressing global challenges and the increasing integration of bioinformatics and protein research into multidisciplinary fields focused on global development.

Among the SDG-related publications mentioning UniProt, the majority are aligned with SDG 3 (“Good Health and Well-being”), which accounts for 62.9% of these studies (see Figure 31). The strong association between UniProt-related research and SDG 3 is understandable, given the centrality of protein science to medical and health research, as highlighted also in Figure 30. Proteins are fundamental to understanding disease mechanisms, drug development, vaccine research, and therapeutic innovations (Niazi and Magoola, 2024; Jin et al., 2023; Singh et al., 2023), all of which are critical components of SDG 3. The recent surge in health-related research, especially during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, further amplifies this trend. UniProt's extensive protein sequence and functional data provide researchers with the foundational information needed to explore pathogen-host interactions, immune responses, and biomarker identification, which are pivotal in improving global health outcomes.

The second largest group pertains to SDG 2 (“Zero Hunger”), comprising 20.6% of the SDG-related publications. The significant proportion of publications addressing SDG 2—which focuses on ending hunger, achieving food security, improving nutrition, and promoting sustainable agriculture—also reflects the versatility of UniProt's resources (e.g., Peirats-Llobet, 2023). Proteins are central to agricultural research, particularly in understanding the genetics of crop improvement, livestock health, and the development of biofortified foods to combat malnutrition. Studies aiming to improve crop resilience to climate change, enhance the nutritional content of staple foods, or develop pest-resistant plant varieties rely heavily on protein data to analyse the molecular mechanisms that drive these traits. The Swiss-Prot database, known for its high-quality annotations, is particularly useful for research involving genetic modification and biotechnological innovations in agriculture, where precision is key to ensuring successful and safe interventions. As an illustrative example, Baburam and Feto (2021) used UniProtKB and Swiss-Prot data to identify enzymes to treat soils contaminated with pollutants.

⁴⁷ <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

⁴⁸ Hereafter ‘SDGs-related publications referencing UniProt and its datasets’

⁴⁹ The identification of SDGs-related publication was made using the SciNoBo classification algorithm. Further details are available at: <http://scinobo.ilsp.gr:1997/toolkit>

Figure 31 Distribution of SDGs-related publications by UniProt resources used and SDGs

Source: Authors' elaboration

4.2. Patent analysis

4.2.1. Findings from narrowed patents' analysis

This section presents findings from the narrowed patent analysis focused on identifying UniProt-related keywords **within patents' titles and abstracts**.

Between 2002 and 2021, **a total of 164 patent applications** were filed that explicitly referenced UniProt or one of its resources in the title or abstract.⁵⁰ These patent applications belong to 78 distinct patent families (see Box 4 below the definition). To avoid double-counting, the analysis considers the priority claim of each patent family, i.e., the first patent application ever filed among those belonging to the same patent family. Out of the 78 patent applications under analysis, 33 patents were successfully granted, reflecting the growing importance of UniProt in scientific innovation.

⁵⁰ Patents referencing UniProt or one of its resources were retrieved implementing the following steps: 1) download from PATSTAT all patents that mentioned UniProt or its resources in the title or abstract, 2) restrict to patents first filed between 2002 and 2021, 3) collapse the resulting database using the earliest filing within the DOCDB patent family.

Box 4 Patent applications, families, publication

A **patent application** is a formal submission an applicant makes to a patent office to request legal protection for an invention, which includes detailed technical information, claims, and any necessary drawings. This application initiates the patent examination process, which assesses the invention's novelty and utility before determining whether to grant a patent. Each patent application belongs to a patent DOCDB family.

A **patent DOCDB family** organises related patent applications from different countries that protect the same invention based on a shared "priority" application, often the first filed. This family structure allows patent offices and researchers to track all versions of an invention globally under a unified group. A patent DOCDB family groups one or more patent applications.

A **patent publication** is the official disclosure of the patent application or granted patent, typically made public 18 months after the initial filing. This publication allows the public to access detailed information about the invention and its legal status, even if the application is still under examination.

The patent application publication is distinct from a granted patent; it refers to a patent application that has been made public but has not yet received approval. **Not every patent application results in a granted patent,** which is the official approval that provides legal protection and exclusive rights to the inventor over their invention. In essence, the publication of a patent application indicates that the application is under review, but it does not confer any legal rights or protection until the patent is granted.

Source: Authors

One could argue that the keyword search limited to the title and abstract of patent applications yields a significantly smaller set of patents compared to a search extended to the full text, e.g., including the description and claims. However, while this narrower approach identifies fewer patents, the results are arguably more relevant: patents identified through this method tend to place higher value on UniProt resources, as evidenced by their explicit citation within the title or abstract. Thus, this focus on the title and abstract ensures that only patents directly emphasising UniProt or its resources are captured, which may enhance the relevance of the findings despite the reduced number of patents.

Based on the analysis of title and abstracts of patent documents, the number of patents remained relatively stable for most of this period, but starting in 2019, there was a noticeable surge in patent filing (see Figure below).

Figure 32 Number of citing patents over time (2002-2021)

Source: Authors' elaboration

Among UniProt's various databases,⁵¹ UniProt as a whole and Swiss-Prot were the most frequently mentioned in patent applications, appearing in 45 and 27 filings, respectively (Figure 32). Additionally, UniProtKB was mentioned in 5 patents, while UniRef and UniRef90 were referenced only once each. No patents during the analysed period (2002–2021) mentioned TrEMBL, UniParc, UniRef50, or UniRef100.

Figure 33 Distribution of patents by resource and year

Source: Authors' elaboration **Note:** Patents referencing more than one resource are fractionalised.

The majority of **patent filings referencing UniProt resources** were concentrated in three major intellectual property (IP) jurisdictions: China (CN), Europe (EP, European Patent Office), and the United States (US) (Figure 33). China led the way with 29 filings, reflecting the country's growing investment in biotechnology, bioinformatics, and related fields. Most patent

⁵¹ UniProt, UniProtKB, Swiss-Prot, TrEMBL, UniParc, UniRef, UniRef50, UniRef90, UniRef100.

applications at the IP jurisdictions in China were filed by universities (21), such as the Zhejiang University of Technology and only to a smaller extent by companies (6).

Europe (EP) followed with 11 patent filings, indicating the strong presence of advanced research institutions and biotech companies across the continent, particularly in countries like Germany, e.g., Roche Diagnostics GMBH, and Switzerland, e.g., Nestec SA. The European market has historically been a hub for pharmaceutical research, biotechnology, and the life sciences, where resources like UniProt play a crucial role in driving innovation. The United States accounted for 10 filings, emphasising its continued leadership in biotechnology and bioinformatics. The U.S. patent filings reflect the robust research ecosystem supported by leading academic institutions, private industry, and governmental research programs.

Figure 34 Patent document jurisdiction

Source: Authors' elaboration **Note:** AU: Australia, CN: China, DE: Germany, EP: European, FR: France, GB: United Kingdom, GR: Greece, IT: Italy, JP: Japan, PL: Poland, RU: Russia, US: United States, WO: World.

UniProt resources have made significant contributions to patents across various technological fields (see Figure 34), with the majority of patents concentrated in Chemistry, followed by Instruments and Electrical Engineering. More specifically, patents citing UniProt resources have largely focused on innovations in Biotechnology. A smaller yet important share of patents citing UniProt data were related to Organic Fine Chemistry, Pharmaceuticals, and Analysis of Biological Materials. Computer Technology is another field in which UniProt data plays a crucial role. Interestingly, the patent data reveals that only a small portion of patents pertained to Food Chemistry. Similarly, there has been limited use of UniProt data in the field of Medical Technology.

Figure 36 Network of patent citations

Source: Authors' elaboration **Note:** Each circle represents a patent. Orange circles are the patents that mentioned a UniProt resource, and the blue circles are patents that mentioned the patents citing UniProt. The size of the orange circles is proportional to the number of mentions it received. The direction of the arrows from patents that mentioned a UniProt resource to patents that mentioned the patents citing UniProt show the knowledge flow. Orange arrows highlight that a patent citing a UniProt resource was mentioned by another patent that also mentioned a UniProt resource. Purple arrows highlight that a patent citing a UniProt resource was mentioned by another patent that did not mention a UniProt resource.

The downstream impact of patents citing UniProt resources also reveals an expansion in technological fields over time. While the patents directly mentioning UniProt or its resources focused largely on Biotechnology, Pharmaceuticals, and the Analysis of Biological Materials, evidence shows that in the later stages, they were cited by a growing number of patents that focused on Medical Technologies. This trend, as shown in the figure below, indicates that **knowledge originating from UniProt-related patents has started to influence areas beyond their original technological scope, fostering innovation in a wider range of fields.** Such spillover effects demonstrate the transformative potential of foundational biological data

resources like UniProt in driving long-term technological growth and cross-disciplinary innovation.

Figure 37 Evolution of knowledge creation from UniProt to patents

Source: Authors' elaboration

4.2.2. Findings from extended patents' analysis

This section presents findings from the extended patent analysis focused on identifying UniProt-related keywords **within patent documents, including descriptions and claims.**⁵³

Between 1988 and 2022, **over 183 thousand patent publications** were filed that explicitly mentioned UniProt or one of its resources in the title, abstract, description, or claims. These patent publications belong to 44,747 distinct patent families (see Box 5). To avoid double-counting, the analysis considers the priority claim of each patent family, i.e., the first patent application ever filed among the patent publications belonging to the same patent family. Out of the 44,747 patent applications under analysis, 43.3% of patents were successfully granted, whereas the remaining 56.7% are still pending.

⁵³ Patents referencing UniProt or one of its resources were retrieved implementing the following steps: 1) download from ORBIS IP all patents that mentioned UniProt or its resources in the title, abstract, description, or claims, 2) collapse the resulting database using the earliest filing within the DOCDB patent family.

Over time, the number of patents has steadily increased (see Figure below). This increase can be attributed to a growing recognition of the value of UniProt in fields such as bioinformatics, drug discovery, and biotechnology, where access to comprehensive protein data has become crucial for advancing research and product development. As a matter of fact, UniProt was recognised as one of the GBC Biodata resources.⁵⁴

The slower rate of filings earlier on can be explained by the typically lengthy and complex patenting process, which involves extensive research, legal reviews, and regulatory considerations. Additionally, it may have taken time for industries to fully grasp the potential of UniProt’s resources and incorporate them into commercial applications. The fact that over 19 thousand patents were granted suggests that, over time, innovators were able to demonstrate the novelty and industrial applicability of their inventions, meeting the stringent criteria for patent approval.

Figure 38 Number of patents over time (1988-2022)

a) Number of patents filed by earliest filing year

b) Cumulative number of patents ever published

Source: Authors' elaboration

⁵⁴ SIB news: <https://www.sib.swiss/news/three-sib-knowledge-bases-recognized-as-critical-for-life-science-worldwide>

Among UniProt’s various databases,⁵⁵ Swiss-Prot is the most frequently mentioned in patent applications, appearing in 24,118 patent applications (53.9%). While Swiss-Prot is historically the most mentioned resource, starting from 2016, the number of patent applications mentioning the UniProt database as a whole has exceeded those mentioning Swiss-Prot. As a result, in 2022, 1,980 (46%) mentioned UniProt as a whole, whereas 901 (21%) mentioned Swiss-Prot. This prominence highlights their central role in scientific research, as both databases provide high-quality, manually curated protein information that is essential for scientific and commercial innovation. Additionally, UniProtKB was mentioned in 7,228 patents (16.2%), reflecting its growing importance as a resource for understanding protein sequence and functional data.

In contrast, TrEMBL, UniRef and UniParc were referenced, respectively, in 985 (2.2%), 270 (0.6%), and 121 (0.3%) patent applications (see Figure 38), indicating that their use in patentable innovations may be more specialised or less well-established in this context, possibly due to the specific functions these databases serve. For instance, TrEMBL is automatically annotated and does not offer the same level of manual curation as Swiss-Prot, making it less appealing for patent applications, which typically require highly accurate, curated data. Similarly, UniParc, which serves as a comprehensive protein sequence archive, and UniRef databases, which focus on sequence clustering, might not yet be recognised as critical tools in innovation-heavy industries, or their utility may not translate as directly to patentable inventions. This trend suggests that while some UniProt resources are invaluable to innovation, others may still be in the early stages of being fully integrated into commercially viable research.

Figure 39 Evolution of patents by resource and year

⁵⁵ UniProt, UniProtKB, Swiss-Prot, TrEMBL, UniParc, UniRef, UniRef50, UniRef90, UniRef100.

Source: Authors' elaboration **Note:** Patents referencing more than one resource are fractionalised.

The majority of **patent filings referencing UniProt resources** were concentrated in three major intellectual property (IP) jurisdictions: the United States IP (32.1%), the World Patent IP (20.5%) and the European IP (10.8%) (Figure 39). These filings in the United States, the World Patent IP and Europe highlight the **global scope of UniProt's influence**, as well as the importance of protecting intellectual property in regions that have heavily invested in biotechnology, pharmaceutical research, and bioinformatics.

Figure 40 Patent document jurisdiction

Source: Authors' elaboration **Note:** AR: Armenia, AU: Australia, BR: Brasil, CA: Canada, CN: China, DE: Germany, EA: Eurasian Patent organization, EP: European, ES: Spain, IN: India, JP: Japan, KR: South Korea, MX: Mexico, US: United States, WO: World.

UniProt resources have made significant contributions to patents across various technological fields (see Figure 40), with the vast majority of patents concentrated in Chemistry (95%), followed by Instruments and Electrical Engineering. More specifically, patents mentioning UniProt resources have largely focused on innovations in Biotechnology and Pharmaceuticals. This highlights the pivotal role of **UniProt in advancing cutting-edge biotechnology applications**, such as genetic engineering, protein therapeutics, and diagnostics. These areas form the backbone of modern biomedical research, where reliable, curated protein information is critical for developing new therapies, diagnostic tools, and biotechnological processes.

A smaller yet important share of patents citing UniProt data were related to Organic Fine Chemistry, Food Chemistry, and Analysis of Biological Materials. These fields leverage UniProt's

protein data for applications such as drug development, molecular analysis, and chemical synthesis. While they represent more niche areas compared to Biotechnology, their reliance on accurate protein data underscores **UniProt’s value in experimental and laboratory-based research across a diverse array of scientific domains.**

Computer Technology is another field in which UniProt data starts playing a role. The growing integration of bioinformatics tools and databases like UniProt into computational models demonstrates how essential protein data has become for computational biology and systems biology. These fields often rely on large datasets and sophisticated algorithms to analyse biological information, making resources like UniProt indispensable for innovations in data-driven biological research.

Figure 41 Technological fields of patents mentioning UniProt resource

Source: Authors’ elaboration

Overall, patents were filed by over 10 thousand entities, including mainly companies and universities. The number of patents filed per applicant widely varies across filing organisations, and the number ranges from 1 to 960. The top five applicants (i.e., filing organisations) are Genentech Inc. (US,960), F. Hoffmann-La Roche AG (CH, 948), Novozymes A/S (DK, 705), Institut National de la Santé et de la Recherche Medicale (FR, 589), and Novartis AG (574)

Beyond the immediate technological fields, **UniProt has had a considerable indirect impact by contributing to additional knowledge creation through patent citations.** Out of the 44,747 patents citing UniProt resources, 17,459 were later mentioned by other subsequent

137,363 patent publications that belong to 76,082 patent families, creating a patent citation network that reflects UniProt's ongoing influence on innovation (see Figure 10 UniProt Impact Pathways). Interestingly, only 5,264 out of the 76,082 (6.9%) citing patent families also mentioned UniProt or its resources, whereas the remaining 70,818 mentioned patent families that mentioned UniProt without mentioning UniProt themselves.

As in the narrower patent analysis, **the downstream effects of patents referencing UniProt resources highlight a broadening of technological domains over time.** Patents mentioning UniProt or its resources are concentrated in Biotechnology, Pharmaceuticals, and the Analysis of Biological Materials. However, among subsequent citing patents, there was a notable increase in patents related to Medical Technologies and Computer Technology. As illustrated in the figure below, this trend suggests that knowledge derived from UniProt-related patents is extending beyond its original technological boundaries, fostering innovation across diverse fields. These spillover effects underscore the significant role of foundational biological data resources like UniProt in promoting long-term technological advancement and interdisciplinary innovation.

Figure 42 Evolution of knowledge creation from UniProt to patents

Source: Authors' elaboration

4.3. Other enablement benefits

Qualitative evidence from user surveys and interviews suggests that UniProt contributes to innovation by supporting the development of new products, services, processes, and ideas that improve upon existing solutions. However, these contributions are not always captured by traditional outputs such as publications or patents (as discussed in previous sections). Survey respondents noted that UniProt facilitates collaboration between industry and academia. While a small percentage of users reported they could not have proceeded without UniProt, a larger share indicated they would have experienced significant delays in their work. Similar feedback emerged regarding the drafting of research publications and the development of processes, products, and services, pointing to UniProt’s practical relevance in these contexts (see Figure 42). Box 5 provides specific examples of products or services developed using UniProt data.

Figure 43 What if UniProt did not exist?

Source: Authors’ elaboration on UniProt users’ survey. **Note:** The figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents and excludes undergraduate and graduate students. Respondents were asked to answer the following question: *In a scenario without UniProt, how would you be able to carry out the following activities within your organisation?* Percentage labels are displayed only for values above 3% to enhance readability.

A significant aspect to consider is the role of UniProt in supporting the emergence of spin-offs and start-ups within the life sciences sector. This sector is typically characterised by an ecosystem of SMEs and start-ups focused on knowledge production, many of which exist primarily to provide services to other companies. These firms often face constraints in

accessing highly skilled researchers capable of advanced knowledge production and thus rely on collaborations with other SMEs to support innovation or to carry out analysis and modelling based on complex research data. Unlike patents or academic publications, these contributions are difficult to trace and are often considered "silent" inputs to innovation. Nonetheless, both interview evidence and survey feedback suggest that UniProt plays a meaningful role for several of these organisations. Many report a substantial reliance on Open Data, with UniProt representing an estimated 5–10% of their overall data pool. In a few cases, companies have indicated that their services are heavily reliant on UniProt, and in some instances, its data has been central to the business model from the outset.

Box 5 Examples of products and services developed using UniProt data

We conducted a text analysis of the open-ended responses to the users' survey question: 'Please provide an example of product or service development for which having access to UniProt was crucial' in order to identify and present a few examples of the most common products and services developed by the respondents (in the IPL, *long-term outcomes* not otherwise identifiable). The results were as follows:

Proteomics tools and services (e.g. mass spectrometry platforms, protein identification tools)

Bioinformatics software and algorithms (e.g. functional annotation tools, protein structure prediction, machine learning models)

Specialised databases (e.g. UniProt-integrated resources, domain-specific protein databases)

Drug discovery tools (e.g. target identification platforms, structure-based design tools)

Functional and structural protein analysis (e.g. target selection tools, protein processing analysis)

Genomic and genetic research tools (e.g. gene expression analysis platforms, variant interpretation tools)

Educational and scientific outputs (e.g. training materials, scientific publications)

Biotechnological applications (e.g. recombinant protein expression systems, antibody production)

Data integration and interoperability services (e.g. identifier mapping, data harmonisation tools)

Web-based applications (e.g. online portals offering protein-related data)

Research support tools (e.g. experimental planning aids, workflow management tools)

Source: Authors' elaboration on UniProt users' survey.

5. Conclusions and lessons learnt

5.1. Conclusions

This case study aimed to test the cost-benefit analysis framework tailored by Delugas et al. (2023) to assess Open Science projects and practices. To carry out this analysis, we relied on a comprehensive set of qualitative and quantitative methods for data collection and analysis. Primary data on costs and usage were obtained from the UniProt Consortium, while information on users was gathered through a user survey. Additional qualitative insights emerged from numerous interviews and focus groups conducted throughout the analysis, which helped validate our findings.

The analysis started with the construction of the impact pathways framework - based on Dekker, Karasz et al. (2023)—to illustrate how the funding and resources provided to UniProt (inputs) lead to direct user benefits (outputs and outcomes) and drive advancements (impacts) in science, the economy, and society. This allowed us to identify both short- and long-term outcomes, as well as wider socio-economic impacts, associated with UniProt and sketch the main UniProt Impact Pathways Logic.

The CBA was employed specifically to evaluate the short-term outcomes UniProt provides to its users, such as time and cost savings. However, a broader causal pathways analysis was used to assess long-term outcomes, acknowledging that these outcomes often involve multiple contributing factors, making it difficult to establish a direct causal link to UniProt. Specifically, UniProt's long-term outcomes were tracked through patent and publication analyses, while other outcomes—such as the emergence of startups—were identified using more qualitative evidence sources, including interviews and user surveys.

It was not possible to carry out a full-fledged CBA for UniProt due to challenges in reconstructing setup and operational costs prior to 2017. Nonetheless, we applied the CBA approach to assess whether UniProt's benefits outweighed its operational costs over the 2017–2023 period. **This comparison revealed the 'net' benefits that UniProt delivers to its users. Key findings from this analysis can be summarised** as follows:

- **Highly labour-intensive initiative:** while it avoids the expenses related to constructing physical facilities, UniProt demands a larger investment in personnel. Indeed, personnel costs incurred by the UniProt consortium account for a significant share (70.91%) of the expenses required to operate this resource.
- **User Community Costs for know-how development:** UniProt entails certain costs for the user community. First, users invest time in learning the platform, which represents a training cost that can take various forms. Additionally, they spend time using the

resources and efforts in community contributions, such as submitting corrections, updates, and new protein sequences to enhance the UniProt database.

- **Significant efficiency gains for the users community:** The primary short-term benefits of UniProt use consist of efficiency gains, which translate into time and cost savings. Three main types of efficiency gains were identified: (i) reduced time spent in negotiating access to alternative data sources (transaction costs savings); (ii) more efficient access methods provided by UniProt compared to multiple, fragmented resources (access cost savings); (iii) time saved in work and research activities (labour costs savings), enabling significantly more efficient processes than alternative options. Labour cost savings represent the most significant of the three efficiency gains examined in this analysis. These savings arise from the continuous efforts of the UniProt Consortium to improve the accessibility of UniProt data, enhance interoperability, and manually annotate the sequences included in Swiss-Prot.
- **Positive Net Benefit:** The results of the cost-benefit analysis indicate that UniProt's net benefit far exceeds the annual investment required to maintain the resource. Specifically, each user experiences a net benefit ranging from 3,513 EUR (based on the lower bound estimation) to 5,475 EUR (upper bound estimation) in a year.

Beyond the short-term outcomes, UniProt plays an **important role in accelerating scientific research and innovation in various forms, thereby contributing to the creation of new knowledge**. To explore the long-term outcomes of knowledge generation associated with UniProt, we complemented the CBA findings with a publication and a patent analysis. These analyses evaluated how the knowledge enabled by UniProt's data contributes to the production of new publications and innovations. **These analyses examined how data provided by UniProt supports the development of new research outputs and innovations**. The results indicate a positive contribution: UniProt and its resources have been cited in over 15,200 scientific publications and referenced in more than 183,000 patent documents across 44,747 distinct patent families. Furthermore, 164 patent applications explicitly mention UniProt or its resources in the title or abstract, suggesting a central role in certain patented innovations. Additional long-term effects—such as the facilitation of collaborations between academia and industry, and the emergence of new entrepreneurial ventures (including spin-offs and start-ups)—were also reported through user surveys and interviews, even if these impacts are not directly captured in publications or patent records.

Overall, employing the CBA approach to estimate the net value generated by UniProt for society—capturing its short-term outcomes—enabled the measurement of user efficiency gains that are typically intangible and difficult to quantify directly, such as the time researchers save thanks to expert curation and integrated data management. In this respect, the estimated value highlights that the true worth of Open Resources lies not merely in their openness, but also in their structure and meticulous curation. These features enhance data usability, reduce

research duplication, and ultimately accelerate scientific discovery, thereby justifying continued investment and reinforcing the socio-economic relevance of UniProt.

5.2. Lessons learnt

This case study has also necessarily shed light on the methodological and conceptual challenges inherent in evaluating Open Resources. While the issues encountered are grounded in the specific context of UniProt, they are representative of a broader set of difficulties relevant to similar open infrastructures embedded in comparable ecosystems. These insights are summarised below:

1. **While estimating individual users of Open Resources presents challenges, meaningful progress is possible with thoughtful approaches beyond simply improving data access.**

Open Resources like UniProt do not typically monitor individual usage. Demand must be inferred from web metrics such as unique IP visits. Yet these metrics are inherently flawed: a single IP may represent multiple users, and a single user may generate multiple IP addresses. Automated traffic further distorts figures. Addressing this requires robust correction mechanisms that must be adapted to each resource's specific features.

→ *OS resources that want to implement CBA assessment protocols should incorporate standardised for adjusting web traffic data, drawing on established benchmarks, and considering collaborative arrangements with infrastructure providers to improve the granularity and accuracy of usage metrics.*

2. **Secondary users of Open Resources are diverse and not always directly traceable, yet they play a critical role in the broader research ecosystem.** Two distinct categories emerge:

- *Cross-reference beneficiaries*, such as those using Gene Ontology annotations supplied by UniProt, form part of an interdependent ecosystem. This reciprocal exchange of data is crucial for the advancement of biomedical science, as the entire ecosystem depends on data sharing and reuse. For cost-benefit analysis purposes, these secondary users will be considered balanced or "cancelled out" since they are present on both sides of the equation.
 - *Indirect beneficiaries* of services built on UniProt data cannot be ignored, as their gains are additive. Although these users are difficult to identify comprehensively, partial tracing is achievable through data collection from direct users. In practice, this results in a conservative, lower-bound estimate of the Open Resource's total user base.
- *When multiple layers of users are present, and it is considered relevant, OS resources that want to implement CBA assessment protocols should invest in mapping value chains of data*

reuse and encourage data intermediaries to collect and share metadata on downstream use, which can help capture secondary impact layers more systematically.

3. Establishing an appropriate counterfactual is not straightforward but essential.

Estimating the incremental value of openness requires a clear counterfactual scenario. For UniProt, this meant rejecting a universal “closed” counterfactual, which lacks empirical grounding, in favour of scenario-based comparisons. Rather than estimating the value of openness per se, the analysis compares integrated Open Resources to fragmented, siloed alternatives. However, the door remains open to future studies applying more targeted closed-open comparisons for specific UniProt data types.

→ *When feasible, evaluators' efforts undertaking a CBA assessment of an OS resource should build modular counterfactual frameworks, allowing tailored comparisons across data types, access models, and user contexts to improve the relevance and credibility of valuation results.*

4. Attributing costs to open bioscience resources demands a nuanced, structured approach. Two key characteristics must be accounted for:

- *The value-added dimension:* Open Resources like UniProt incorporate extensive curation and annotation, often relying on distributed user contributions. These contributions must be monetised where relevant for CBA.
 - *Collaborative production models:* Most open bioscience resources emerge from extensive collaboration. To ensure a balance between costs and benefits, the analysis must account for these collaborations and the types of contributions provided without double-counting historical or sunk costs. Financial and in-kind contributions related to the ongoing operation of the resource are within scope; historical and routine expenditures unrelated to data sharing are not.
- *To improve cost estimation, funders and operators of OS resources that want to implement CBA assessment protocols should carefully keep track of the financial flows related to the open project from the very beginning of the project, also maintaining disaggregated cost reporting structures overtime that distinguish between operational and in-kind contributions—facilitating more accurate impact assessments.*

The publication and patent analysis of UniProt also yielded critical operational lessons:

5. Tracking usage in scientific literature and patents is indispensable and presents an opportunity to harness AI-powered tools for more effective, scalable analysis.

Drawing on the UniProt publication and patent analysis, key lessons have emerged that should inform and improve future applications of these methods—especially as AI capabilities continue to advance.

- Since internal usage tracking is not available, a dual-method strategy combining surveys and keyword-based searches is essential. While surveys provide valuable direct insights, they have limitations such as incompleteness and self-reporting bias. Conversely,

carefully designed and refined keyword searches enable broader coverage and scalability, especially when enhanced by AI-driven text mining and natural language processing techniques. Meticulous keyword selection is critical to minimise false positives and maintain relevance.

- Similarly, search parameter choices materially affect the quality and breadth of results. Full-text searches maximise coverage but risk including marginal references; abstract/title searches yield fewer but more relevant results. Combining both approaches might be preferred to strike a balance between breadth and depth, ensuring that both frequent and significant uses are captured.
 - ➔ *To facilitate this type of analysis, OS resources should put effort into developing a harmonised keyword system and exploring automated tools for continuous tracking of citations across publications and patent databases. At the same time, evaluators conducting patent analysis should always report the sensitivity of their findings to search strategies and adopt layered search techniques to distinguish between different degrees of use cases.*

6. Quantifying causal impact requires more than citation counts but bring robustness in the analysis.

While usage statistics provide evidence of reach, they fall short of demonstrating UniProt's contribution to innovation. Causal inference requires user feedback via surveys and interviews to contextualise usage and understand how critical UniProt data were to scientific and technological outputs. Without this, the value attributed to UniProt risks being overstated or mischaracterised.

- ➔ *OS resources aiming to implement impact assessment protocols should integrate causal evaluation tools into project cycles. This includes using tailored surveys to gather both quantitative and qualitative data for building causal inference models, as well as incorporating case studies and user narratives as standard elements of performance assessments.*

7. The selection of the unit of analysis in patent analysis critically shapes conclusions.

Whether one counts patent applications, publications, families, or priority claims alters the inferred magnitude of impact. Broader units, like applications, can exaggerate influence, narrower ones, like families, risk underrepresenting dissemination. The choice must be justified and aligned with the analysis objective, ensuring analytical rigour and interpretive clarity.

- ➔ *Evaluators conducting patent analysis should predefine units of analysis based on the policy question at hand and, where feasible, triangulate results across units to validate findings and reduce bias.*

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Annexes

1. Methodological toolkit

The assessment presented in this deliverable draws upon a comprehensive and multi-dimensional methodological approach that integrates both primary and secondary data sources, as well as qualitative and quantitative analytical techniques. The objective was to produce a robust, evidence-based evaluation of UniProt's value and impact. The methodological toolkit comprises a set of interconnected components, each offering distinct but complementary insights. Desk research provided the foundation for mapping impact pathways, stakeholder groups, and evaluation approaches. Web traffic data were used to estimate the scale of the user base to be used in the CBA model. The user survey offered detailed information on usage patterns, perceived value, user benefits that are not otherwise quantifiable, and scenarios without UniProt. Time monetisation enabled the quantification of short-term benefits and user-incurred costs for the CBA. Semi-structured interviews and focus groups added qualitative depth and served to validate the findings, while citation and patent analyses offered insight into the longer-term scientific and innovation-related impacts.

The sections that follow present each methodological component in more detail.

A.1.1 DESK RESEARCH

Desk research was the first step of the assessment and was conducted by using academic paper, policy reports, and other grey literature. It pursued a manifold objective and focused on three different strands of literature to inform the assessment:

- 1. Historical and performance analysis.** It related to the history, gradual development, usage, and performance of the resources under assessment, along with their individual components. This review was essential for identifying the impact pathways associated with these resources, mapping the diverse types of stakeholders that potentially benefit (e.g., the scientific community, PhD students, private sector, funding agencies, and government bodies) and outlining all stakeholders involved in the financing and operation of these resources.
- 2. Impact evidence.** This component reviewed the publicly available evidence regarding the impacts of UniProt, including prior evaluation studies and internal materials (e.g., survey results). The objective was to take stock of existing evidence and build upon it to inform the current assessment.
- 3. Methodological framework.** The literature related to the evaluation of similar Open Resources was consulted to refine and enhance the methodological framework employed for assessing UniProt, ensuring that best practices and lessons learned from similar evaluations were incorporated into the analysis. Some examples of relevant literature consulted in this phase include: Beagrie and Houghton 2021; 2016, 2014;

Koudouri et al. 2021; Sweeny et al. 2017; Sullivan et al. 2017; Lauer et al., 2021; Garcia et al., 2018 Klebel et al 2024; Fell, 2019.

A.1.2 ANALYSIS OF THE WEB TRAFFIC DATA.

In general, Open Resources—such as UniProt—do not monitor individual users directly. As a result, any estimation of user demand must be inferred from web traffic data, specifically by counting the number of unique visitors identified through IP addresses accessing the resource. However, as widely acknowledged in the literature (e.g. Ross et al., 2024; Beagrie and Houghton, 2021, 2016; Fomitchev, 2010), there are important limitations to this approach. Unique visitor counts may not correspond accurately to actual user numbers, as multiple individuals (e.g. researchers from the same institution) may share a single IP address, while a single user may appear under several IP addresses (e.g. due to access from different locations, multiple devices, or dynamic IP allocation by internet service providers). Moreover, such counts may include automated visits by bots or web crawlers. It is therefore necessary to apply appropriate methods to estimate the number of actual users from raw web traffic data.

To estimate the number of users, we relied on statistics from browser and programmatic access provided by UniProt consortium (reported in Figure 2, Section 1), as these provide a more complete and accurate estimation of the user base. Following the methodology proposed by Beagrie and Houghton (2021), the following steps were adopted:

1. *Adjustment for COVID-19 Effect for the year 2020.* The browser and programmatic access data are available for the period from 2019 to 2023 due to legal requirements (see Figure 2). This five-year trend reveals a significant peak in 2020, likely attributable to the increased use of multiple devices for accessing UniProt. To account for this COVID effect, we followed the approach suggested by Beagrie and Houghton (2021), allowing the 2019 figure to grow by only half (7.5%) of the registered increase (15%).
2. *Reduction for Overestimation.* Fomitchev (2010) reports that unique IP addresses and unique cookie counts overestimate unique visitors by a constant factor that increases linearly with the duration of sampling. This overestimation can reach up to 80 times within a year. As a result, our second adjustment involved conservatively reducing the annual count of unique visitors by a factor of 80.
3. *Adjustment for Unregistered Access.* A very small fraction of users accesses UniProt in ways that are not registered by data logs, such as via FTP or certain APIs.⁵⁶ Following Beagrie and Houghton (2021), we applied a correction factor of 2.5% per year to represent this proportion of users.
4. *Estimating the number of users for 2018 and 2017 years.* Since our analysis covered the period from 2017 to 2023 and browser and programmatic access data was only available

⁵⁶ FTP refers to File Transfer Protocol and is a method for moving files between computers on a network, while API indicates Application Programming Interface that is a set of rules or protocols that enables software applications to communicate with each other.

from 2019, we needed to estimate the number of users for the years 2017 and 2018. This estimation was conducted by applying the growth rate derived from the browser access data, which was available for the period 2017-2023, to the browser and programmatic access data.

Our calculations yield an average of approximately 107,000 users per year over the period 2017–2023. We have also compared our estimates to external sources to triangulate the reliability of our results, following the comprehensive approach of Beagrie and Houghton (2021, 2016). The 2021 UNESCO Science Report estimates that, by 2018, there were 8.854 million full-time equivalent (FTE) researchers worldwide. Beagrie and Houghton (2021) applied a factor of 25% to estimate the number of FTE researchers in the life sciences, based on Australian R&D expenditure data disaggregated by field of science. Using this method, the potential number of FTE researchers in the life sciences globally is approximately 2.2 million. This figure represents the maximum potential user base of UniProt, bearing in mind that not all of these researchers focus on protein-related topics. Our user estimate thus represents around 5% of this potential base, and should be interpreted as a lower-bound estimate.

A.1.3 USER SURVEY

It was addressed to gather deeper insights into user profiles (i.e. age, professional background, etc.), the purposes for which they use the resources (including any other sources used in conjunction), existing alternatives (if any), and primary data on the perceived value of these resources. The survey was implemented using the EUSurvey tool.

The questionnaire was structured in four sections: Section A – General Information: it investigated respondents' profile (e.g. country of work, professional status, sector of activity, research fields/job details, etc); Section B – Experience with the resources: it investigated on the usage of the resources (e.g. frequency, combination with other sources, etc); Section C – the value of the resource: it included questions investigating the time spent in accessing the resource, processing and work with it as well as the additional time that it would have required to manage agreement, access, process and work with alternatives; Section D – Overall opinion: it collected views on the importance of the resource and examples of innovations developed.

The survey was disseminated through UniProt, EMBL-EBI, SIB, and ELIXIR websites, social media, newsletters, and industry programmes. A few pilot tests (5-6) were conducted with selected users to gather feedback on the questionnaire's clarity. Overall, 558 responses⁵⁷ were collected between 26th March and 6th May 2024.

Since the characteristics of the user base population are entirely unknown—apart from the global geographical distribution of users inferred from web traffic data—it was decided not to adopt a probability sampling approach. Instead, a thorough ex-post analysis was carried out,

⁵⁷ Out of 558 respondents, 38 never used UniProt and 10 are former users. Additionally, one respondent abandoned the survey. Therefore, the final sample considered to support this assessment includes 509 complete responses.

comparing the distribution of respondents by country with that of web traffic data, alongside a comparison of respondents' sectors of activity and primary research fields with statistics from desk research based on publications and patents.

Given the close alignment between the country-level composition of survey responses and that of the web access data, as well as the consistency in terms of research fields and economic activities and supported by constructive discussions with the UniProt consortium to validate the comparison, we consider the survey sample to be sufficiently reliable for use in the subsequent cost-benefit analysis, including with respect to other user characteristics.

Nonetheless, certain limitations of the approach should be acknowledged. First, the absence of a defined sampling frame and the reliance on voluntary participation introduce potential self-selection bias, as those more actively engaged with the resource may have been more inclined to respond. Moreover, given the dissemination channels used, the sample is likely to be more representative of users based in Europe, the United States, and other countries where UniProt is most widely used. Second, although efforts were made to validate the representativeness of the sample through comparisons with web traffic data and desk research, unobservable differences may still limit the generalisability of the findings.

A.1.4. ESTIMATING THE VALUE OF TIME

The monetisation of time represents the core methodological approach adopted to quantify the short-term outcomes associated with the use of UniProt resources, specifically in terms of cost savings. The monetary value of time was estimated using data from the user survey on reported time savings, combined with hourly wage estimates by professional role and country. These wage estimates were drawn from a combination of sources, including Payscale, Glassdoor, and the Economic Research Institute—three commercial databases offering publicly accessible benchmarks for a wide range of job titles. In addition, Eurostat and OECD statistics on average weekly hours worked by sector were used to convert annual salary figures into hourly rates.

The approach adopted to monetise the value of time—from both cost and benefit perspectives is the following.

The first step involved **quantifying the average time per person for each benefit or cost** as follows:

Let f_{iq} be the absolute user frequency for each time range i of the question q .

Let v_{iq} be the central value of each time range i of the question q .

Let N_q be the total number of non-missing answers for the question q .

The total weighted hours T_q used or saved can be calculated as:

$$T_q = \sum_i f_{iq} \times v_{iq}$$

The average hours saved or used per respondent \bar{t}_q is then:

$$(1) \quad \bar{t}_q = \frac{T_q}{N_q} = \frac{\sum_i f_{iq} \times v_{iq}}{N_q}$$

The second step involved **quantifying the most conservative hourly salary** associated with each \bar{t}_q .

Once obtained the hourly salary by role⁵⁸ and country by means the salary benchmarks, we computed a country-weighted hourly salary by role as follows:

Let C be the set of countries of survey respondents.

Let $S_{j,c}$ be the average hourly salary for role j in country c

Let f_c be the 2019-2023 average relative frequency of unique visitors by country c .⁵⁹

Let R be the set of roles proposed by questions A2.1 and A2.2.

The average weighted hourly salary by role \bar{S}_j can be calculated as:

$$\bar{S}_j = \frac{\sum_{j \in R} \sum_{c \in C} S_{j,c} \cdot f_c}{\sum_{c \in C} f_c}$$

The average weighted hourly salary by role \bar{S}_j has then been used to obtain the value of each \bar{t}_q . Instead of computing the median or average hourly salary across the roles to monetise all the different costs and benefits, we allow the value of time to vary based on the user's frequency distribution. This approach takes into account that different job profiles may use UniProt with varying intensity and frequency of time, thus causing the time to have a different value.

For each question q :

Let \bar{S}_j be the weighted salary mean for role j .

Let $f_{j,tq}$ be the role frequency for a range of time t for the question q .

Let T_q be the set of time ranges for the question q .

For each question q , the weighted salary means by range of time \bar{S}_{tq} is:

$$\bar{S}_{tq} = \frac{\sum_{j \in R} \bar{S}_j f_{j,tq}}{\sum_{j \in R} f_{j,tq}} \text{ with } t = 1, 2, \dots, T$$

The final hourly salary for each question q is the more conservative figure between the median \bar{S}_q or the average \bar{S}_{tq} of the \bar{S}_{tq} previously calculated for any of the T_q range of time.

$$(2) \quad S_{bq} = \min(\bar{S}_q, \bar{S}_{tq})$$

$$(3) \quad S_{cq} = \max(\bar{S}_q, \bar{S}_{tq})$$

Completed the steps, the value of time for each cost and benefit is computed by combining equations (1) and (2) for the benefits and (1) and (3) for the costs.

$$V_b = S_{bq} \times \bar{t}_q$$

$$V_c = S_{cq} \times \bar{t}_q$$

A.1.5 INTERVIEWS

To complement the information gathered through the user survey, a total of 13 interviews were conducted. The interviews were conducted with selected users from both industry and academia to gather evidence on (i) the purposes for which UniProt is used; (ii) the sources with which data from UniProt are typically combined; (iii) the practices used for the storage of data (locally/ cloud services/open repositories, for how long, etc.); (iv) challenges faced by users in accessing or integrating UniProt; (v) the perceived impact of UniProt on users' research

⁵⁸ The main roles covered by users from academia include: research assistant / postdoc, research fellow / associate, assistant professor / lecturer, associate professor / reader, professor, other. in the private sector, the roles covered by users include: principal investigator, wet lab researcher, computational biologist / bioinformatician, director / manager, analyst, clinician, database curator, consultant, software developer and other.

⁵⁹ Country absolute frequencies are retrieved by UniProt web traffic as explained in Section 1.3

outcomes. The insights gained from these discussions proved valuable in interpreting the survey results and further clarifying and explaining the impact pathways of UniProt.

A.1.6 FOCUS GROUPS

Two focus groups were also conducted to validate and enhance the robustness of the assessment. The first focus group, held on 6th September 2024, aimed to validate the survey results. The second focus group, held on 16th September 2024, focused on eliciting participants' willingness to pay for UniProt through a contingent evaluation survey designed in accordance with the 'NOAA Panel' (Arrow et al., 1993) and the 'Contemporary Guidance for Stated Preference Studies' (Johnston, 2017). The selection of participants relied on contacts provided by survey respondents (a total of 243 contacts) as well as direct contacts from the UniProt consortium and should be understood as qualitative evidence, given the non-random selection of participants.

A.1.7 CITATION AND PATENTS ANALYSES

These analyses were conducted to complement the findings from the CBA and to explore the long-term impacts associated with UniProt. It examined the extent to which the knowledge facilitated by the data provided by UniProt is reflected in new publications and innovations.

It was assessed the extent to which the knowledge facilitated by the data provided by UniProt is reflected in new publications and innovations by analysing references to UniProt and its resources in titles and abstracts of patents and academic publications. To achieve this, mentions of UniProt-related terms—such as UniProt, UniProtKB, UniParc, UniRef (including UniRef50, UniRef90, UniRef100), SwissProt, Swiss-Prot, and TrEMBL — were retrieved for academic publications and patent data. Specifically, for the publication analysis, a search was performed in the titles and abstracts of scientific publications from 2003 to 2022. Data were sourced from OpenAIRE. For the patent analysis, two approaches were adopted. The narrow approach focused on identifying patent applications filed between 2002 and 2021 that mention the same set of keywords in their titles or abstracts, with data sourced from PATSTAT. The extended approach broadened the scope to include mentions in titles, abstracts, descriptions, or claims of patent publications filed since the creation of Swiss-Prot, thus covering the period from 1988 to 2022, using Orbis IP as the data source.

2. Interviews carried out

The following Table reports the round, date, and affiliation of interviewed for each interview carried out.

Table 11: List of interviews

INTERVIEW ROUND	ORGANISATION	DATE
Scoping Interviews	Ontoforce	30/11/2023
Scoping Interviews	Eagle Genomics	05/12/2023
Scoping Interviews	EMBL-EBI	15/12/2023
Scoping Interviews	EMBL-EBI	19/12/2023
Scoping Interviews	Roche	19/12/2023
Value and Impacts	Knowing01	29/04/2024
Value and Impacts	Saphetor	29/04/2024
Value and Impacts	Gencoverly	07/05/2024
Value and Impacts	General Bioinformatics	22/05/2024
Value and Impacts	Datavisyn	06/06/2024
Value and Impacts	University Hospital of Bern	08/07/2024
Value and Impacts	BullFrogAI	15/07/2024
Value and Impacts	Expert Systems	15/07/2024

THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC VALUE OF UNIPROT

Launched in **2001**, and building on previous databases, **UniProt** is a **comprehensive resource on protein data**.

Detailed annotations on protein function, domains, and modifications

Benefitting a vast community of life science researchers across the world

Seamless integration of protein data to other biological databases

Users primarily from North America (23%), Europe (15%), Asia (28%)

Advanced tools for data search, analysis, and visualisation

And from academia (67%), industry (20%)

Globally and freely accessible

Mostly used in the fields of bioinformatics, biomedical technology and pharma

TOTAL AVERAGE ANNUAL COST & BENEFITS

UniProt's operation depends heavily on human expertise (~70% of the expenses).

Total annual costs €14.6 million

Users benefit from time savings in accessing data and conducting research.

Total annual benefits: €373 million – €565 million

POWERING DISCOVERY, INNOVATION AND ECONOMIC GROWTH

Creating new knowledge

15,200+ scientific publications mentioned UniProt and its resources.

Accelerating R&D and innovation

183,000+ patent publications mentioned UniProt and its resources.

Innovations driven mainly in **biotechnology and pharmaceuticals** fields.

UniProt fosters spin-offs and start-ups within the life sciences sector that provide expertise in data manipulation, interpretation, and analysis.

The resource accelerates the development of **new products and technologies**, for example, protein identification, drug target validation, machine learning models.

Pfizer, Genentech, Roche, Novartis, and other global leaders rely on UniProt for bioinformatics-driven discovery.

Supporting the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Scientific publications mentioning UniProt are mostly related to **SDG3 (Good Health and Well-being)** and **SDG2 (Zero Hunger)**.

WHAT IF UNIPROT DID NOT EXIST?

- 74%** Would not have had access to the same data from a closed source
- 68%** Could not have recreated the same data themselves
- 65%** Would have experienced slower publication timelines
- 52%** Said academic collaboration would have been limited

No other resource offers UniProt's unique combination of protein data quality, coverage, and integration.

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